

5GCITY

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D6.4 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardization activities

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0.2	12/05/2019	I2CAT	Individual exploitation plans
0.3	16/05/2019	I2CAT	Dissemination, Communication, Standardization activities added
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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the dissemination, standardization and exploitation activities of the project during the second year of the project (M13 to M24). The information complements that already included in D6.1, D6.2 and D6.3. The document is divided in five sections, first four provides an exhaustive description of the activities and the fifth presents an overview of the progress.

5GCity project has achieved during the last 12 months a relevant position due to the maturity of the research carried out in the project. The impact of the work has raised due to the development of the platform, focused on neutral hosting encompassing different technical topics including optimized edge/core virtualization, network slicing, service orchestration & SDK, that is being validated in three different cities (Barcelona – ES, Bristol – UK and Lucca - IT). Having in mind the achievements developed by the project, the dissemination, standardization and (individual/joint) exploitation activities have been planned to maximise impact and expose the project results.

The strategy the Consortium has applied to execute the dissemination and communication activities during the second year has focused on presenting and demonstrating intermediate results of the research at different events and conferences (being the most important the Mobile World Congress, Smart City Expo World Congress and the SDN/NFV World Congress), in addition to the promotion of project concepts and objectives. Regarding the standardization and exploitation activities during this year the partners have continued the work done during the first year, identifying the joint exploitation of 5GCity opportunities developed inside the consortium, that are presented per city.

1. Introduction

This document reports on the achievements and activities related to communication, dissemination, standardization and exploitation of the 5GCity project in Year 2 (Jun 2018-May 2019).

The document is organized in four chapters corresponding to different types of activities as follows:

- Section 2 reports on the dissemination and communication and public activities undertaken jointly by the consortium and individually by the partners in Year 2.
- Section 3 summarizes standardization activities, partners' strategies and updates towards SDO working on 5GCity related topics, and 5GCity contribution to different open source communities.
- Section 4 details the individual exploitation activities executed by the partners, along with updated plans for rest of the project, in relation to the knowledge and results generated within 5GCity during the second project year. Furthermore, it also details the joint exploitation plans of different partners in the consortium according to their interest, activities, and role in the three cities.
- In last place, section 5 summarizes the key relevant aspects and strategic achievements in this area, and also provides an overview on the level of fulfilment of 5GCity KPIs which have been set in the Description of the Action.

2. Dissemination and Communication Activities

The Dissemination and Communication activities of the 5GCity project have continued during the second year increasing the focus on impact towards the scientific community through publications, and towards potential stakeholders through exhibitions and demonstrations. Activities carried out by consortium partners have continued to consolidate a bold project visibility within the scientific, industrial and vertical community working on 5G.

The consortium and partners individually have kept strong involvement in many activities, in event and conference participation, giving keynote presentations and participating in industry roundtables. It has produced a significant number of scientific papers and prepared material for key exhibition events of the 5G community. The project communication has stressed evermore the selling points of the project across various channels (website, socials, local communities, large worldwide conferences and exhibitions), to reach the stakeholders in Media and Smart City market areas with highlights and public presentations of the project use cases and the technical results in the architecture and city infrastructure design. The active involvement in the 5GPPP and its various Working Groups (WG), in the 5G Infrastructure Association, and in the 5G community has opened opportunities for the project team to discuss approaches and R&D directions, together with presentations of plans and results.

Top priority has been given to all dissemination and communication activities aimed to document and promote the 5GCity value behind all the efforts and research done.

All the information that is open for the scientific community as public deliverables is shared through a dedicated community in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/5gcity/?page=1&size=20>).

The results achieved in Year 2 are presented below, divided in different dissemination areas:

- Scientific publications
- Participation to talks/Panels/Webinars
- Demonstrations
- 5G PPP collaborations
- Liaison with other Projects
- Communication via Project Web Site
- Communication via Social Networks (twitter, LinkedIn)
- Newsletter and technical blogs

2.1. Scientific Publications

During the second year of project, a total of **13 publications have been submitted, 9 of which at international conferences (ACM or IEEE and in main tracks), 1 journal article, 2 extended abstracts prelude to presentations in EUCNC workshops, 1 poster.** 2 conference papers are under evaluation, 2 papers were rejected. All in all, **9 papers have been accepted** in the period.

The list of papers and scientific publications is reported in **Table 1**.

#	Type	Title	Authors	Conference	Status
1	Paper	Enabling Vertical Industries Adoption of 5G Technologies: a Cartography of evolving solutions	Anastasios Zafeiropoulos, Panagiotis Gouvas, Eleni Fotopoulou, George Tsiolis, Thanos Xirofotos, Stamatia Rizou, Jose Bonnet, Anastasius Gavras, Maria Joao Barros, <u>Gino Carrozzo</u> , Xavier Costa-Perez, Athul Prasad,	EuCNC 2018, Ljubljana, Slovenia, June 18-21, 2018	Published

#	Type	Title	Authors	Conference	Status
			Marco Gramaglia, Anna Tzanakaki, Dimitra Simeonidou, John Cosmas, Mikael Fallgren, Raul Muñoz, Ricard Vilalta,		
2	Paper	5G City: A Novel Distributed Cloud and Edge Platform for 5G Neutral Host	Carlos Colman-Meixner, Shuaib Siddiqui, Paolo Cruschelli, Antonino Albanese, Maria Rita Spada, Teodora Sechkova, Hamzeh Khalili, Luca Vignaroli, David Pujals, Alberto Hernando, Nicola Ciulli, Simon Prior, Alex Mavromatis, and Dimitra Simeonidou	EuCNC 2018, Ljubljana, June 18-21, 2018	Rejected
3	Paper	Edge Computing Enhancements in an NFV-based Ecosystem for 5G Neutral Hosts	Gabriele Baldoni; Paolo Cruschelli; Michele Paolino; Carlos Colman Meixner; Antonino Albanese; Apostolos Papageorgiou; Hamzeh Khalili; Muhammad Shuaib Siddiqui; Dimitra Simeonidou	IEEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks, 27-29 Nov 2018 – Verona, Italy	Published
4	Journal Article	Deploying a Novel 5G-Enabled Architecture on City Infrastructure for Ultra-High Definition and Immersive Media Production and Broadcasting,	Carlos Colman-Meixner, Hamzeh Khalili, Konstantinos Antoniou, Muhammad Shuaib Siddiqui, Apostolos Papageorgiou, Antonino Albanese, Paolo Cruschelli, Gino Carrozzo, Luca Vignaroli, Alexandre Ulisses, Pedro Santos, Jordi Colom, Ioannis Neokosmidis, David Pujals, Rita Spada, Antonio Garcia, Sergi Figerola, Reza Nejabati, and Dimitra Simeonidou.	IEEE Transaction on Broadcasting.	Published
5	Paper	Cloud & Edge Trusted Virtualized Infrastructure Manager (VIM) - Security and Trust in OpenStack	Teodora Sechkova, Enrico Barberis, Michele Paolino	IEEE WCNC19 15-19 April 2019, Marrakech, Morocco	Published
6	Poster	Unleashing the Power of Unikernels with Unikraft	Simon Kuenzer, Felipe Huici (NEC)	SYSTOR 2019 June 3-5 2019 Haifa, Israel	Published
7	Paper	"Computing and Network Virtualization at the Edge for 5G Smart Cities Neutral Host Infrastructures", 28th European Conference on Networks and Communications (EUCNC 2019), June 18-21, 2019, Valencia, Spain	Michele Paolino, Carlos Colman Meixner, Teodora Sechkova, Gino Carrozzo, August Betzler, Hamzeh Khalili, Muhammad Shuaib Siddiqui, Dimitra Simeonidou,	EUCNC 2019, June 18-21, 2019, Valencia, Spain	Rejected
8	Paper	Secure Location-Aware VM Deployment on the	Teodora Sechkova, Enrico Barberis, Michele Paolino	EUCNC 2019, June 18-21, 2019,	Accepted

#	Type	Title	Authors	Conference	Status
		Edge Through OpenStack and ARM TrustZone		Valencia, Spain	
9	Paper	Network Slicing-Aware NFV Orchestration for 5G Service Platforms	Hamzeh Khalili, Apostolos Papageorgiou, Shuaib Siddiqui, Carlos Colman-Meixnerx, Gino Carrozzo, Reza Nejabati, and Dimitra Simeonidou.	EUCNC 2019, June 18-21, 2019, Valencia, Spain	Accepted
10	Extended abstract	Definition and Evaluation of Latency in 5G with Heterogeneous Use Cases and Architectures	Gino Carrozzo, M. Shuaib Siddiqui, Kevin Du, Bessem Sayadi, Oscar Carrasco, Fotis Lazarakis, Janez Sterle, Roberto Bruschi	EUCNC 2019, June 18-21, 2019, Valencia, Spain	Accepted
11	Extended abstract	Path to 5G Smart Cities: Experiences from Media and Public Safety Pilots in 5GCity	Gino Carrozzo, M. Shuaib Siddiqui	EUCNC 2019, June 18-21, 2019, Valencia, Spain	Accepted
12	Paper	Computing and network virtualization at the edge for 5G smart cities neutral host infrastructures	Michele Paolino, Gino Carrozzo, August Betzler, Carlos Colman-Meixner, Hamzeh Khalili, Shuaib Siddiqui, Teodora Sechkova, and Dimitra Simeonidou.+	2019 IEEE 5G World Forum (5GWF), Sept 30 - Oct 2 2019, Dresden, Germany	Submitted
13	Paper	Xuan Du, Gino Carrozzo, Bessem Sayadi, Fotis Lazarakis, M.S. Siddiqui, Oscar Carrasco, Michail Alexandros Kourtis, Janez Sterle, Roberto Bruschi,	Definition and Evaluation of Latency in 5G: A Framework Approach	2019 IEEE 5G World Forum (5GWF), Sept 30 - Oct 2 2019, Dresden, Germany	Submitted

Table 1 - Scientific publication during project Year 2

2.2. Participation to Talks/Panels/Webinars/Workshops

Regarding event participation, the consortium has been represented in **15 important and well-known events** during Year 2, giving presentation, keynotes, panel discussion and demonstrations related with 5GCITY. Other 6 event participations are planned for the period May-November 2018, as described in section 2.8.

The complete list of events with 5GCity participation are reported in the following table.

Title		IoT 2018 - 3rd Cloudification of the Internet of Things Conference	
1	Type	Presentation of Accepted Paper, title: fog05: Unifying the computing, networking and storage fabrics end-to-end.	
	Speaker/Attendees	Angelo Corsaro, Gabriele Baldoni. ADLINK Technologies, France	
	Event	Conference	
	Date	2-4 July 2018	
	Place	Paris, France	

	Link	www.ciot-conference.org/	
2	Title	IBC	
	Type	Presentation, Demo, Dissemination material	
	Speaker/Attendees	MOG, Cellnex	
	Event	Media Industry, Policy Makers, Regulators, Regional and International Organizations, Private Sector, Press	
	Date	13 - 17 Sept 2018	
	Place	Amsterdam, Holand	
	Link	www.ibc.org	
3	Title	Towards 5G Enabled Gigabit Society	
	Type	Presentation	
	Speaker/Attendees	Mariano Lamarca Barcelona City Council	
	Event	ITU Events Policy Makers, Regulators, Regional and International Organizations, Private Sector, Non-Governmental Organizations, Academia.	
	Date	11-12 Oct 2018	
	Place	Athens, Greece	
	Link	https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/Regional-Presence/Europe/Pages/Events/2018/5GForum/Towards_5G_Enabled_Gigabit_Society.aspx	
4	Title	IoT Solutions World Congress 2018	
	Type	Demo/Dissemination material	
	Speaker/Attendees	VOSYS	
	Event	IoT Industry, Policy Makers, Regulators, Regional and International Organizations, Private Sector, Press	
	Date	16-18 Oct 2018	
	Place	Barcelona, Spain	
	Link	www.iotsworldcongress.com	
	Documents	vosysiot_IOTWC2018.pdf	
5	Title	Lucca Comics and Games 2018	
	Type	Booth, Demos, Dissemination material, Presentation	
	Speaker/Attendees	Comune di Lucca, Rai, Nextworks, Italtel, Wind Tre, Comunicare Digitale	
	Event	Millennials, Press	
	Date	29 Oct - 4 Nov 2018	

	Place	Lucca, Italy	
	Link	https://www.luccacomicsandgames.com/it/2018/home/	
	Documents	www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q6APMin2IC0 Lucca_C&GF_5GCITY_TALK2Millennials.pdf	
6	Title	SCWEC	
	Type	5GCity Side Event - Presentations/Demo/Dissemination material	
	Speaker/Attendees	5GCity partner moderation in a dedicated session The Next Level of Connectivity for Industries and Society; in the Digital Transformation. 5GCity consortium was also involved in the organization and implementation of the 5GCity Side Event, with the 5G Smart City Vertical Use Case Awards. IMI/i2Cat/Accelleran showed Barcelona radome operating live with i2cat WiFi APs and Accelleran 3.5GHz LTE Small Cells in Orange spectrum at City of Barcelona Booth	
	Event	Policy Makers, Regulators, Regional and International Organizations, Private Sector, Non-Governmental Organizations and Academia.	
	Date	13 Nov 2018	
	Place	Barcelona, Spain	
	Link	http://www.smartcityexpo.com/en/home	
	Documents	https://www.5gcity.eu/2018/12/11/2069/	
7	Title	20th Infocom World 2018	
	Type	Present the 5GCity Neutral Host business model and the related regulatory considerations	
	Speaker/Attendees	inCITES	
	Event	Workshop on H2020 programs organised by OTE	
	Date	21 Nov 2018	
	Place	Athens, Greece	
Link	https://infocomworld.gr		
8	Title	ICT 2018: Imagine Digital - Connect Europe	
	Type	5GCity Booth/ Presentations/Demo/Dissemination material 5GCity showed-case its Neutral Hosting platform targeting city edge	

	Link	www.mwcbarcelona.com/	
	Documents	www.5gcity.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/MWC2019-5GCity-final-version_Ssv3.pdf	
11	Title	NAB Show	
	Type	Demonstration of new solutions based on the video decentralized production UC	
	Speaker/Attendees	MOG	
	Event	Media Industry, Policy Makers, Regulators, Regional and International Organizations, Private Sector, Press	
	Date	6-11 April 2019	
	Place	Las Vegas, US	
	Link	www.nabshow.com	
12	Title	2nd 5G Forum	
	Type	Presentation	
	Speaker/Attendees	Shuaib Siddiqui	
	Event	Telco industry, Policy Makers, Regional and International Organizations, Private Sector, Academia, Press.	
	Date	24-25 April 2019	
	Place	Malaga, Spain	
Link	https://www.5gforum.es/en/		
13	Title	IEEE International Conference on Computer Communications	
	Type	Workshop about testbeds	
	Speaker/Attendees	Bristol University	
	Event	Industry, Policy Makers, Regulators, Regional and International Organizations, Private Sector, Press.	
	Date	29 April- 2 May 2019	
Place	Paris, France		

	Link	http://infocom2019.ieee-infocom.org/cnert-computer-and-networking-experimental-research-using-testbeds	
14	Title		
	Type	Keynote	
	Speaker/Attendees	Felipe Huici, Simon Kuenzer	
	Event	IEEE UCC 2018	
	Date	18/12/2018	
	Place	Zurich	
	Link	https://conferences.computer.org/ucc/2018/#!/home	
	Documents	Unikraft: Unikernels for Dummies	
		<p>11th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Utility and Cloud Computing 17-20 December 2018 • Zurich, Switzerland</p>	
15	Title		
	Type	Talk	
	Speaker/Attendees	Simon Kuenzer	
	Event	FOSDEM 2019	
	Date	2/2/2019	
	Place	Brussels	
	Link	https://fosdem.org/2019/schedule/speaker/simon_kuenzer/	
	Documents	Unikraft: Unikernels Made Easy	
		<p>FOSDEM 19 beer devrooms open source 8000+ hackers lightning talks 742 lectures Brussels 2 & 3 February 2019</p>	
	Title		
	Type	Talk	
	Speaker/Attendees	Simon Kuenzer	
	Event	LISA 2018	
	Date	30/10/2018	
	Place	Nashville	
	Link	https://www.usenix.org/conference/lisa18/presentation/kuenzer	
	Documents	Unikraft: Unikernels Made Easy	
		<p>LISA18 is a wrap! October 29-31, 2018 Nashville, TN, USA Thanks for joining us in Nashville for LISA18. Video, audio, and presentation slides are posted on the conference page.</p>	
16	Title		
	Type	Talk	
	Speaker/Attendees	Florian Schmidt	
	Event	Open Source Summit Europe 2018	
	Date	21/10/2018	
	Place	Edinburg	
		<p>THE LINUX FOUNDATION October 22-24, 2018 Edinburgh International Conference Centre Edinburgh, UK #OSSummit</p>	

- 5GCity UC4: UHD Video Distribution - immersive services Demo
- MWC 2019
 - 5GCity Platform: Network slicing and service provisioning demo
 - 5GCity UC3: Video acquisition and production Demo
 - 5GCity RAN: Load balancing in LTE Small Cells

2.4. 5G PPP Collaborations and 5G IA activities

Regarding the liaison with 5G PPP projects and the participation to 5G PPP activities, the consortium has actively contributed to various Working Groups and events, participating to the planned face to face meetings and task forces with continued support.

In particular, 5GCity has participated to key Working Groups of the 5G PPP through designated representative partners as briefly reported in the following table:

Area	Working Group	5GCity representative	Main activities
5G PPP	Steering Board	i2CAT (S. Figuerola and S. Siddiqui) - PC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Coordination with other projects ● Annual Program report ● MWC2019 and EUCNC 2019 coordination ● Face to face meetings ● Periodic conference calls
5G PPP	Technical Board	NXW (G. Carrozzo) TM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Completion of Project cartography ● Project KPIs analysis and assessment with focus on two KPIs (Latency and Service Creation Time) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Coordination of work on Service Creation KPI with other Phase 2 Projects ○ Contribution and editing of 2 papers on Latency KPI ● Cross-project technical coordination ● Contribution to Phase 2 Golden Nuggets collection and presentation task force ● MWC19 and EUCNC 2019 technical contributions ● Face to face meetings ● Periodic conference calls
5G PPP	5G PPP COMMS	CODI (C. Bressan)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Coordination of participation and promotion of activities at ICT 2018, MWC2019, EUCNC 2019 ● Periodic conference calls ● Update of project news and activities into 5G PPP web portal
5G PPP	Architecture	Italtel (A. Albanese)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Discussion and contribution to the new 5G PPP Architecture whitepaper ● Periodic conference calls ● Face to face meeting
5G PPP	Network Management and QoS	UW (T. Batista)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Discussion of a new Network Management whitepaper ● Periodic conference calls
5G PPP	Software Networks (SDN/NFV)	UW (R. Preto) i2CAT (S. Siddiqui)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Discussion on new SDN/NFV whitepaper ● Collection of Open Source contributions by the 5G PPP projects ● Periodic conference calls

5G IA	Pre-standards	BCN IMI (M. Lamarca)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fog05 presentation • Periodic conference calls
5G IA	Trials WG	NXW (N. Ciulli) i2CAT (S. Figuerola)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trials pre-structuring model and follow ups • Contribution to Trial roadmap 4.0 • Periodic conference calls
5G IA	Security	VYOSYS (M. Paolino) i2CAT (S. Siddiqui)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on new Security whitepaper • Periodic conference calls
5G IA	Vision and Societal Challenges	INCITES (T. Rokkas)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Periodic conference calls
Networld 2020	SME WG	NXW (N. Ciulli, G. Carozzo)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation of SME brochure for EUCNC'19 • Preparation of SME success stories for 5G PPP web portal • SME coordinated presence and dissemination at EUCNC'19 • Periodic conference calls

Table 2 – 5GCity collaborations within 5G PPP area

The relation with 5G PPP teams has continued to be productive and regular. Interactions between 5GCity and the 5G PPP on social network platforms (LinkedIn, Twitter) have strengthened, as stated by the high number of 5G PPP re-tweets and posts related to 5GCity relevant topics.

2.5. Liaison Activities with Projects

Also in this second year, the consortium has continued effective collaborations with other projects of the 5G PPP programme. In particular, the following collaborations have occurred and can be reported:

- Towards 5G-TANGO (Involved partners: **i2CAT, NXW, UW**):
 - Current collaboration on Service creation Time KPI definition within 5G PPP TB
 - Discussion of 5G Catalogue and SDK models in use
 - Preparation of joint special session to EUCNC'19 on
- Towards NGPaaS, MATILDA, 5G ESSENCE (Involved partner: **NXW via 5G PPP TB**):
 - Joint work on Latency KPI evaluation framework and submission of conference papers
- Towards NRG-5, 5G ESSENCE, 5G-MEDIA (Involved partner: **NXW, i2CAT, WindTre**)
 - Organization of the Special Session 3 5G trials for vertical industries at EUCNC' 19
 - Plans to organize joint activities on media use cases (common area of work)
- [Extra 5G PPP] Towards 5G UK Hub and 5G Barcelona (Involved partner: **i2CAT, UniV Bristol**)
 - Synergies for the development of the 5G infrastructures in Bristol and Barcelona, link to 5GCity use cases and territory
 - Joint visibility with 5G Barcelona @ MWC19
 - Planned 1st 5GCity Hackathon in Bristol also to strengthen links with 5GUK

2.6. Communications via public Web Site

Since the project beginning on June 2017, 5GCity's website (<http://www.5GCity.eu>) plays a major role in the dissemination & communication activities of the 5GCity consortium. The website contains all the information about the 5GCity activities (past, on-going, upcoming), developments, and results.

Figure 1 – 5GCity.eu landing webpage

The main objectives of the 5GCity website are:

- To build & deploy constant and permanent information and data to help 5GCity dissemination and promotion;
- To distribute information, data, presentations, news, ideas periodically to keep high the attention upon the project;
- To public, making available through the project’s website all dissemination material (flyers, rollups, press releases, etc.);
- To circulate the information from all partners to amplify the power of the various activities;
- To strengthen an enlarge the networking, media & press contacts, creating a “5G universe”;
- To be visible and active online, offline, and in the public sphere of relations of the “5G universe”;

For this purpose, after the restyling occurred in 2018, a regular flow of blog entries, newsletters, news, reports and videos from the participation to events attended has implemented.

New announcements on the project website are summarised in the following pictures.

All information released from the website is licensed via a Creative Commons license (likely the “CC BY” license) for maximum dissemination and use of licensed presentations.

As expressed in prior deliverables, the consortium plans to maintain the web site active for a minimum of two years after project’s end in order to ensure the sustainability of the project results.

2.7. Communications via Social Networks

Right after the MWC 2019, a new 5GCity communication campaign was launched through the socials and website to maintain high the interest among 5G community and attract new peers and millennials over 5G and 5GCity activities.

5GCity @5GCity · 29 mar
 Neutral Host model offers a new business model for sharing 5G infrastructure.
 5gcity.eu @ginocarozzo @MShuaibSiddiqui @Michele_Paolino @NinoAlbanese
 @mariaritaspada @GoClearNow @sfiguerola @ComunicareDigit @_gabry
 @p_khodashenas @Dsimeo @Global5Gorg @5GPPP
 Traduci il Tweet

Andrea Michelozzi · 1er
 Ceo Dime Comunicaciones SI
 3 semanas

5GCITY presents Neutral host model, Live Pilots in 3 cities (Barcelona, Lucca, Bristol), new services for citizens as videosurveillance and video analytics for public safety (LUCCA), Connected cars (UW) and RAN virtualization.

Empowering Cities Infrastructures! www.5gcity.eu

Gino Carozzo Nicola Ciulli Gianluca Insolubile Carla Bressan Lorenzo Michelozzi Sergi Figuerola, PhD Shuaib Siddiqui Pouria Sayyad Khodashenas, Ph.D. Hamzeh Khalili, Ph.D Daniel Camps Jose Miguel Sanjuan Marroquin, PhD Michele Paolino Gabriele Baldoni Antonino Albanese Rita Spada Luca Vignaroli Accelleran ADLINK Technology Oscar Pallarols Cellnex Telecom David P. Sergi Alsina Gonzalez betevé Rai - Radiotelevisione Italiana Comunicare Digitale i2CAT Foundation wind tre Dimitrios Xydias, CFA inCITES Consulting Italtel Paola Cortellessa MOG Rui A. Costa Ubiquitous NEC Corporation

Ver traducción

Top media Tweet earned 1,779 impressions

Have you watch the new 5G video w/ @sfiguerola @mariaritaspada @NinoAlbanese and @Iuvignaroli (in italian) on 5gcity.eu? Thanks to @SmartCityexpo and @WindTreOfficial @5GPPP @ginocarozzo @MShuaibSiddiqui @ComunicareDigit @5GBarcelona @UK_5G @Dsimeo pic.twitter.com/y3SuVpW6ns

4 5

Top Tweet earned 2,869 impressions

5GCITY is proud to present: the 5G Neutral Host Platform. Join us during #MWC19 in Barcelona @5GPPP @i2CAT @cellnextelecom @ComunicareDigit @acceleran @NextworksSrl @ADLINK_Tech @Italtel @ginocarozzo @sfiguerola @MShuaibSiddiqui @NinoAlbanese @Michele_Paolino @acorsaro pic.twitter.com/AbmzND537v

1 21 30

Top Follower followed by 32.4K people

5G Security & Privacy
 @Trusted5G FOLLOWS YOU

#Cybersecurity, #CyberKinetic #Security & #Privacy of #5G, #SDN, #NFV & connected #CyberPhysical infrastructure #IoT, #IIoT, #ICS, #CriticalInfrastructure

Analytics

from 5GCity Social Media: 5G Twitter (@5gcity)

At the present time (May 2019) the account has reached **1.527 followers** – still 1st place among 5G EU projects with 49.9k (March 2019) impressions, stimulating website visits (+ 28% - March 2019).

@5gcity 5GCity

2,841 tweets **167** following **1,527** followers **28** listed

Joined Twitter on May 15, 2017 as user #864226108786528258

This project receives funding from the @EU_H2020 Research & Innovation Programme.

<http://www.5gcity.eu> Barcelona - Bristol - Lucca

5G LinkedIn Group

In the 5GCity LinkedIn Group, the number of participants has increased in the last months, moving from 106 in February to 130 members in April 2019; shaking group activities, stimulating discussion and networking, reaching new members (going from 130 in April to 140 by June).

Carla Bressan · 1st
Comunicare Digitale
1mo

Pleased to share brand new 5GCity video to be shown during MWC2019. Read complete MWC2019 press release with all 5GCity activities and demos on: www.5gcity.eu ...see more

Shuaib Siddiqui
Director Software Networks,
Fundació i2CAT [5GCity]

With the 5GCITY solution the broadcaster can assure a temporarily dedicated high quality connectivity, even in demanding circumstances, to facilitate real-time transmission in remote locations for a certain event or news coverage.

Newsletters and Technical Blog

Newsletters have been regularly produced. On April 2019, the 5GCity 4th Newsletter was published on the project Website , on the Twitter (<https://twitter.com/5GCity/status/1118596531257581568>) and LinkedIn accounts. It was also published and shared on the 5GPPP website(<https://5g-ppp.eu/5gcity-newsletter-4/>)

https://twitter.com/5GCity/status/1118596531257581568

5GCity @5GCity
Following

The new #4 @5GCity Newsletter is born! Read it 5gcity.eu/news-events/. Upcoming events in Malaga @5G_FORUM Lucca @ForumLucca and Valencia @EuCNC @5GPPP

21:26 - 17 apr 2019

5GCity @5GCity · 17 apr
New papers published in 5GCity website 5gcity.eu/papers/ thanks to @NinoAlbanese @Michele_Paolino @ginocarozzo @sfguerola @HamzehKhalili @MShuaibSiddiqui @Dsimeo @mariantaspada @luvignaroli @incitesCons @acceleran @5GPPP @IEEEESmartCities @IEEEorg

Cloud & Edge Trusted Virtualized Infrastructure Manager (VIM)

5G - ENABLED ARCHITECTURE ON CITY INFRASTRUCTURE FOR UHD AND IMMERSIVE MEDIA PRODUCTION AND BROADCASTING

5G PPP
The 5G Infrastructure Public-Private Partnership

5GCity Newsletter #4

2.8. Updated dissemination plan for next period

As part of a continuous planning and improvement of the 5GCity dissemination actions, in Year 2 a significant number of events have been prepared and targeted.

Some of these events have offered the opportunity for 5GCity consortium to keep showcasing demos, testing 5G equipment, providing UHD video shooting opportunities for city use cases tests. While other will give the opportunity to disseminate at European level project's results and achievements consolidating what it has been done during Year 1 and as natural conclusion of project itself.

The list of events planned for 2019 is presented in Table 3.

#	Data & Location	Event	Planned attendees
1	6-7 June 2019 Lucca, Italy	16th European Digital Forum www.forumeuropeo.tv/en/ 5GCITY SHOW AREA, Video & demo material, Panel participation, Dissemination material, Meetings.	ALL Partners Media Industry, Policy Makers, Regulators, Regional and International Organizations, Private Sector, Press.
2	18-21 June 2019 Valencia, Spain	EUCnC 2019 https://www.eucnc.eu/ 2 papers accepted; Presentations in a special session; Business Model Workshop presentation; Presentation in Software Networks WG workshop: "Path to 5G smart cities: experiences from media and public safety pilots in 5GCity", Dissemination material; Indoor booth; Demos: 5GCity SDK + Platform, Mobile backpack video transmission (beteve); Video Acquisition and Production (MOG); 5 mobile handsets number of cores at the edge; Augmented Reality service (Rai)	ALL Partners Policy Makers, Regulators, Regional and International Organizations, Private Sector, Non-Governmental Organizations and Academia, Media.
3	12-17 Sept 2019 Amsterdam, Holland	IBC2019 https://show.ibc.org/ Presentation, Demo, Dissemination material	Partners Media Industry, Policy Makers, Regulators, Regional and International Organizations, Private Sector, Media
4	29-31 Oct 2019 Barcelona, Spain	IoT Solution World Congress 2019 https://www.iotsworldcongress.com/ Demo/Dissemination material Partners	Partners IoT Industry, Policy Makers, Regulators, Regional and International Organizations, Private Sector, Press
5	30 Oct - 3 Nov 2019 Lucca, Italy	Lucca Comics and Games 2019 https://www.luccacomicsandgames.com/it/lcg/home/ Booth, Demos, Dissemination material, Presentation	Comune di Lucca, Rai, Nextworks, Italtel, Wind Tre, Comunicare Digitale Millennials, Press
6	24-27 Feb 2020 Barcelona, Spain	MWC 2020 www.mwcbarcelona.com/ Presentation, Dissemination material, 5G business questionnaire. Demos: -Neutral host for 5G infrastructure concept along with the current status of the project. - Neutral Hosting solution with media related use cases: The Video Acquisition & Production.	ALL Partners Telco industry, Policy Makers, Regulators, Regional and International Organizations, Private Sector, Non-Governmental Organizations and Academia, Press.

		www.5gcity.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/MWC2019-5GCity-final-version_SSv3.pdf	
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Table 3 - 5GCity planned participation to upcoming events

2.9. Other dissemination activities: hackathons and Xen blog.

Moreover, from the abovementioned events and activities, after June 2019, 5GCity will concentrate efforts in particular during the events as listed in the following table.

Date & Location	Event	Attendees
9-12 July 2019 Bristol, UK	1st 5GCity Hackathon Use and hack 5GCity slices Structure: 5GCity tutorial (platform+dashboard+sdk) Demonstrate 1 5GCity use case on SDK launch your service design session /module implementation (e.g. monitoring exporters)	Partners industrial community around 5G students
18-22 Nov 2019 Lucca, Italy	2nd 5GCity hackathon and 8th ETSI OSM Hackfest https://osm.etsi.org/wikipub/index.php/7th_OSM_Hackfest#OSM_Hackfest_Sessions OSM Hackfests co-located with OSM Plenary and mid-release meetings. Parallel hackathons from OSM and 5GCity OSM traditional scope 5GCity scope: tutorial (platform+dashboard+sdk); Demonstration of 1 5GCity use case on SDK; Launch your service design session /module implementation (e.g. monitoring exporters)	Partners industrial community around 5G students
31/01/2019	Xen Project Blog	Xen Project Celebrates Unikraft Unikernel Project's One Year Anniversary (https://xenproject.org/2019/01/31/xen-project-celebrates-unikraft-unikernel-projects-one-year-anniversary/)

Table 4 –5GCity partners attendance to additional events

3. Standardization and Open Source Project Activities

Following the strategy described in deliverable D6.2 “Standardization and Exploitation Plan”, the standards related activities of the project during Year 2 have been mostly focused on consolidating engagement with the identified SDOs in the four main areas (edge computing, 5G, cloud/orchestration and media), and setting the ground for 5GCity contributions until the completion of the project.

3.1. Edge Computing and Smart Cities

The number of consortium and standardisation groups that have initiatives around IoT continue to grow and mature. A clear example is that by the beginning of 2019, the Industrial Internet Consortium (IIC) and the OpenFog Consortium have finalized the details to combine efforts and become one international consortium in Industrial IoT, fog, and edge computing. The organizations will work together under the IIC umbrella. The goal of the combined consortium is to drive the momentum of the industrial internet, including the development and promotion of industry guidance and best practices for fog and edge computing [ICC-OpenFog-Merge].

3.1.1. 5GCity contribution to Eclipse IoT Consortium

In the context of the 5GCity project we are working with the Eclipse IoT Consortium to establish an ecosystem of technologies as well as a reference platform for MEC and Fog Computing. Below the list of activities that we have performed during the second year of the project.

3.1.1.1 Eclipse Cyclone DDS Project

During Year 2, ADLINK has continue to contribute to the Eclipse Cyclone DDS, which is an implementation of the OMG Data Distribution Service (DDS) specification (see <http://www.omg.org/spec/DDS/>) and the related specifications for interoperability (see <http://www.omg.org/spec/DDS-RTSP/>)

The contribution activity and commits on this project during the last 12 months can be seen in the official Eclipse page of the project [cyclone-dds]. Eclipse Cyclone DDS offers unique data-sharing capabilities compared to the already existing Eclipse solutions (i.e. for messaging).

3.1.1.2 Eclipse fog05 Project

As it was presented in D6.3, 5G-City is contributing to accelerate the adoption of MEC and Fog Computing, for that reason ADLINK has continue to develop the Eclipse IoT project named fog05, that provides and infrastructure for Fog Computing and MEC.

Eclipse fog05 provides a virtualised infrastructure that allows to distribute computing, storage, control and networking functions closer to the users along a cloud-to-thing continuum. From this description it should be clear that fog05 can leverage cloud infrastructure or equally function without it.

The contribution activity and commits on this project during the last 12 months can be seen in the official Eclipse page of the project [eclipse-fog05]. The source code can be accessed in the following repository <https://github.com/eclipse/fog05>.

3.2. 5G/RAN

In Year 2, ACCELERAN has continued its participation to the Small Cell Forum, in 2018 it was awarded the SCF Award “Outstanding Innovation in Small Cell Architecture or Technology” for their “Carrier and mission critical grade architecture agnostic RAN/vRAN solutions”. This achievement is an industrial award and is

related to R&D activities in scope with 5GCity, which will also stimulate subsequent contributions to SCF Release documentation packages focused on Small Cells. (<http://www.accelerant.com/accelerant-scf-award-winner/>).

3.3. Cloud and Orchestration

The main activities of the Year 2 in this area have been carried out by partners working on the 5GCity orchestration and NFVI functions (NXW, i2CAT, UW, VYOSYS, ADLINK) who have analysed the latest standard releases by ETSI NFV on NS and VNF package descriptions and by MEC (for co-existence of MEC in NFV) in order to align 5GCity design of SDK and edge/core virtualization infrastructure to the latest international recommendations by ETSI.

During the period Year 2, there was an accepted contribution to ETSI OSM that consisted on a VIM connector for the Eclipse fog05 (Implementation of *vimconn_fos*), the source code has been accepted and merge to the upstream. This contribution was led by ADLINK. To find more details of this contribution please visit: <https://osm.etsi.org/gerrit/#/c/7368/>

NXW has been contributing to Specialist Task Forces set up by ETSI to work on gap analysis between OpenStack APIs and NFV interfaces, and on MEC Testing Framework. This activity has configured as a mix of standardization and exploitation tasks.

3.4. Media and Broadcasting

In the Year 2, the media vertical partners of 5GCity (RAI, Barcelona TV) have continued following the activities of AMWA, EBU, Society of Motion Pictures Engineers, Digital Video Broadcasting and ITU. The EBU more specifically the 5GCP working group gathers members and the industry to identify requirements in content production that need to be met in the 5G context. In this context 5GCity vertical partners are contributing to identify such requirements with the UC5 - BTV Mobile Backpack integration tests with Accelleran 3.5GHz Small Cell. (<https://tech.ebu.ch/groups/5gcp>)

3.5. Collaboration with Open Source Communities

During the second year of the project, 5GCity consortium members have made a number of contributions to the open source community.

- Ongoing contribution to the Unikraft project, led by NEC, it has been bootstrapped as Xen Project under the Linux Foundation. Since February 2019, the releases of Xen Project, 4.10.3 and 4.9.4 series, are available at <https://xenproject.org/2019/02/25/xen-project-4-10-2-and-4-9-3-are-available-2/>. There is also an open-source repository (<http://xenbits.xen.org/gitweb/?p=unikraft/unikraft.git>) and a public wiki have been setup to ease engagement with the community of developers and adopters (<https://www.xenproject.org/developers/teams/unikraft.html>).
- Accepted contribution to ETSI OSM, ADLINK developed aVIM connector for Eclipse fog05 Implementation of *vimconn_fos* for Eclipse fog05 VIM, the source code has been accepted and merge to the upstream. To find more details of this contribution please visit: <https://osm.etsi.org/gerrit/#/c/7368/>
- Ongoing contribution to the ETSI OSM, release five. The partners NXW, UW, i2CAT have continuously held technical discussions, testing and supporting operations supporting the OSM R3, R4 and R5.

-
- In a similar way, in February 2019, 5GCity was acknowledged in the ETSI MEC White Paper No. 20, in the Annex B - Collaborative projects related to MEC. This reference to 5GCity project is a public recognition of the effort and impact of 5GCity in the community. The main topic of the white paper is “Developing Software for Multi-Access Edge Computing - 2nd edition”. **[ETSI-whitepaper]**.

4. Exploitation Activities

4.1. Partners' Individual Exploitation Activities

4.1.1. i2CAT

Fundació i2CAT is a non-profit technology centre that promotes R&D and Innovation activities in the field of Information and Communication Technologies and the Future Internet. The strategic objectives of i2CAT are: (i) to integrate research, development and innovation; (ii) to foster co-creation using the Quadruple Helix model; (iii) to develop activities within hybrid international and regional framework; and (iv) to create networking and multimedia infrastructures and advanced experimental platforms.

Two research areas, namely Software Networks (SN) and Mobile Wireless Internet (MWI) are actively involved in 5GCity project. As stated in D6.2, i2CAT plans its exploitation strategy along four lines, including i) In-house SDN/NFV tool enhancement, ii) Wireless network virtualization, iii) Leverage for future projects, and iv) Knowledge and technology transfer.

i2CAT is already progressing with the four lines of effort for its exploitation strategy. With regards to SDN/NFV tool enhancement, i2CAT is focused on improving its expertise on the Open Source MANO (OSM) orchestrator which is also supported by ETSI. To achieve this, SN team members are closely following the development activities of OSM by attending OSM F2F meetings. Furthermore, SN team is also looking in to the fog05 edge orchestrator for possible integration with OSM in order to support end-to-end service orchestration in city edge infrastructures. The team is also working on using the above orchestrations tools with OpenStack (Cloud management) and ODL (SDN controller). All in all, these activities are enriching the in-house expertise of the SN with regards to SDN/NFV tools.

The MWI team is working on the enhancement of the wireless network virtualization components and the generation of assets, in particular, the i2CAT SDN-based RAN controller. When looking at the different components that form the RAN controller, there have been improvements of the wireless scheduler agent running in the Wi-Fi nodes and in the RAN controller. The scheduling features is required to enable assigning ratios when slicing the RAN and evaluations have been carried out for new designs of the scheduler to align with SoA wireless driver developments. Similarly, the work on the global scheduler (in the SDN controller) has been continued, to the point that the scheduling system as a whole (local + global scheduler) could be validated. Further, MWI team members have dedicated efforts on integrating the i2CAT RAN virtualization components running in the wireless nodes with elements from other partners, such as the fog05 edge orchestrator. A common NETCONF management and control interface was defined that integrates both Small Cell and Wi-Fi node control and management plane, allowing for i2CAT's SDN controller to configure both types of devices. Overall, the RAN controller that aggregates all of aforementioned features will be the main asset generated in 5GCity, to be exploited in future projects. As such, it will undergo optimizations and additions of further modules, such as a telemetry module that allows the extraction of radio-related status information, as well as additions to support more radio technologies.

i2CAT considered various 5GCity platform components to serve as basis for a wide-scale enhanced 5G KPIs validation platform. In addition, plans are under discussion to leverage on 5GCity platforms for future projects under the umbrella of 5GBarcelona.

i2CAT has already identified 5GCity platform as an asset for the organization as it is very aligned with the requirements and goals of 5GBarcelona initiative which is led by i2CAT. As mentioned earlier, the plan is to further enhance 5GCity platform, for example, to include validation mechanisms for particular technological KPIs, for 5GBarcelona.

i2CAT plans to keep progressing along the abovementioned four lines of exploitation. For SDN/NFV tool expertise, the plan is to complete development and integration of new modules with OSM and fog05 and possibly contribute these developments back to OSM and fog05 communities. The main targeted OSM enhancements are related to i) the ability to orchestrate Virtual Networks within the context of 5G end-to-end network slicing of multi-access networks, ii) the support of a broader palette of infrastructure management technologies, iii) a more efficient coordination with Multi-access edge computing orchestrators, and iv) more efficient resource placement algorithms.

4.1.2. NEC

NEC has been pursuing a number of promising domains related to its Unikraft technologies:

- Public services: NEC is developing, in conjunction with the city of Lucca, a PoC aimed at leveraging NEC's automated, machine-learning based image recognition algorithms to automatically detect illegal waste detection and potentially report the activity in real time to the police. A first proof of concept is working, and we're currently in the process of deploying the necessary infrastructure in Lucca to run a fuller test.
- Automotive: we're in talks with potential partners such as ARM who are interested in Unikraft for automotive since it's security properties and its small trusted compute base mean potentially inexpensive certification processes.
- Edge and IoT: we're in the early stages of introducing Unikraft to NEC's platform business units who are interested in Unikraft's ability to generate extremely small and lean virtual machines and containers.

4.1.3. VOSYS

Smart cities, servers and objects connectivity create important opportunities but also exposes human beings to high risks at a point that a cyberattack could stop an entire country, as reported by a recent article from BBC (<https://www.bbc.com/news/business-45952693>). As a result, we are today experiencing an increasing market demand of virtualization, safety and security solutions in edge and 5G systems. For this reason the VOSYS exploitation activity in 5GCity aims at building a vertical VIM-NFVI product solution which enables trusted computing and mixed criticality features in 5G networks. Such product is VOSYS TrustedVIM (<http://www.virtualopensystems.com/en/products/vosystrustedvim/>), developed as a result of 5GCity and derived directly from the 5GCity EdgeVIM component.

TrustedVIM is based on company system partitioner product VOSYSmonitor (<http://www.virtualopensystems.com/en/products/vosysmonitor/>), a certified system partitioner for embedded systems and resources constrained devices that enables workloads virtualization and certification in mixed critical environments. With TrustedVIM, VOSYS ambitions to secure the safety critical part of the 5G infrastructure, thus addressing the emerging market of 5G security (including verticals like Industrial, IoT, Connected Vehicles, healthcare, etc).

Finally, VOSYS will leverage skills and expertise acquired during the project activities (trusted computing, Virtualized Infrastructure Managers, Arm architecture, virtualized systems, 5G networking, etc.) to provide related design and development services

4.1.4. ADLINK

ADLINK has been pursuing to impact different open source communities in the fog/MEC domains:

- ADLINK has been working on an integration with the Open Source Management and Orchestrator (OpenSource MANO) to contribute to the OSM project with an initial implementation of vimconn_fos for Eclipse fog05 VIM, in the branch Resource Orchestrator (RO) of OSM project. The tracking history

of this open source exploitation can be found at:
<https://osm.etsi.org/gerrit/#/q/status:open+project:osm/RO+branch:fog>

- ADLINK has continue to contribute to the Eclipse fog05 project, which provides end-to-end compute, storage and networking virtualisation. The opensource repositoty can be found at:
<https://github.com/eclipse/fog05>

4.1.5. Cellnex ReteVision

Cellnex Telecom, as the leading infrastructure provider in Europe, has focused his innovation strategy around 5G technology. Due to the expected increase of urban population in the developed countries, 5GCity shows clearly the path for 5G technology deployment.

Expected outcomes from 5GCity project for Cellnex are in two different lines:

- The first one is to learn and to establish internal procedures for **5G rollout in urban environments**, in tight collaboration with municipalities, mobile operators, manufacturers, service providers, etc. Operational model, business model, and specific technical solutions will be designed based on the project results.
 - In this line, dedicated and specific studies have been conducted **during 2019** jointly with the *Institut Cerdá* in order to define the best approach.
- The second one is the direct **commercialization of the infrastructure elements** that have been put in place for the project, such as small cells solutions for Radio Access Network (RAN), integrated with urban-based MEC elements and integration procedures with mobile networks. This commercialization will be in two ways.
 - Infrastructure provision to cities/municipalities aiming to deploy neutral host infrastructures to avoid multiple 5G urban dense networks, and then offered to the mobile operators.
 - Service providers/verticals aiming to offer dedicated services to urban citizens based on the 5G-based neutral host infrastructure.

Cellnex Telecom has already started to take advantage of both lines, as it has become key partner for strategic 5G trials, such as the ones funded by Spanish Government, for **expected rollout during 2020**. In the same line, dedicated trials with music festivals and similar organizations are under preparation during the **first half of 2019**, all of them self-funded, that will test the capabilities of those infrastructure elements. Furthermore, specific rollouts for 5G infrastructure components have been **already started** from Cellnex in several countries like France, Switzerland or the Netherlands, based on the existing or new locations in urban areas to be reused by multiple operators.

Finally, for the six coming months, there's no significant change expected in the existing plans, although further projects are planned due to the relevant impact of 5G strategy in Cellnex Telecom.

4.1.6. University of Bristol

5GCity work at University of Bristol is hosted by the High-Performance Networks (HPN) Group. HPN group is researching about the next generation optical transmission, new optical data centre solutions and architectures, software defined networks (SDN), network function virtualization (NFV), cloud and edge computing, mobile edge computing (MEC), 5G technologies, Internet-of-things (IoT), and Smart City ICT solutions.

Moreover, HPN Group is part of the University of Bristol's Smart Internet Lab¹, a unique interdisciplinary research hub, combining more than 200 digital experts from around the world.

One of the main targets of Smart Internet Lab is to develop all necessary technologies and their interconnection to enable smarter cities and a better digital life for citizens. Therefore, new technologies researched and developed together in 5GCity project may be relevant for the Smart Internet Lab and will be considered to be introduced, maintained and exposed to its public and stakeholders in its smart city testbeds. The University of Bristol as part of the 5G urban showcase and as part of West of England Combined Authority to install 5G mobile technology and demonstrate use cases of immersive reality in the Roman Baths in Bath, Bristol's MShed museum and science centre We the Curious. As most 5GCity testbed elements has been installed in Bristol's MShed to enrich the 5G urban showcase.

Regarding future innovation, the University of Bristol is working in partnership with TM Forum, an industry association leading digital business transformation, and Bristol City Council to develop the Bristol Institute for Digital Futures. As this one develops, it will adopt and co-develop TM Forum's Open Digital Architecture (ODA) and Open APIs as an architectural foundation to its emerging laboratory. TM Forum's defacto-standards provide an open, industry-endorsed approach to connecting the burgeoning number of industry vertical digital ecosystems. Neutral Hosting and Smart City services, systems and platforms will profit from those developments. This provides a good base for alignment with the 5GCity project and potential exploitation and reuse of its developments.

4.1.7. Nextworks

During the second project year, Nextworks' role of core NFV MANO technology provider and developer has consolidated, with particular impact on three major areas of foreground:

- **5GCity orchestration platform**, with focus on the integration with ETSI OSM NFV MANO, the 5GCity Multi-Tier Orchestration towards MEC, and the integration with Monitoring platforms
- **5GCity Service Development Kit**, which eases the way Verticals edit and compose Functions into Services, abstracting the complexity of NFV descriptors
- **5GCity infrastructure design, deployment and operation**, with particular focus on aspects of multi-VIM deployment options, integration of core and edge computing, use of constrained devices at edge and far-edge.

The design and NFV profiling work carried out with 5GCity use case development teams in the area of City surveillance (UC1 – Unauthorized Waste Dumping Prevention), immersive and participatory media services (UC3 - Video Acquisition/Production and Community media engagement in live events, UC4 - UHD Video Distribution and Immersive Services) has further matured and the various showcases prepared for ICT2018 event, MWC2019 and EUCNC2019 have further increased the research team's expertise on VNF/Function and NS/Service modelling with focus on aspects of routing, monitoring, scaling.

The acquired know-how and the various showcases in international events of the highest visibility have contributed to further increase Nextworks visibility in the 5G Community, which also stimulated the creation of new business opportunities with some key stakeholders:

- Standard Development Organizations (ETSI NFV and ETSI MEC)
- Operators interested in executing 5G trials (in Italy and beyond Europe)
- Creation of new partnerships for joint participation to tenders on NFV service roll-out and operations

¹ <http://www.bristol.ac.uk/engineering/research/smart/>

During Q3-2018/Q2-2019, Nextworks team has secured 3 new services contracts with ETSI to participate in Specialist Task Forces (STF) formed by ETSI to cover specific topics of the NFV and MEC workprogramme:

- Technical support 4th ETSI NFV Plugtests running in the period Dec-2018 / Jun-2019
- ETSI STF 563 on OpenAPI Specifications for NFV running in the period Jan-2019 / Dec-2019
- ETSI STF 569 on MEC API Conformance Test Specifications running in the period May-2019 / Jan-2020, originated as a continuation of the ETSI Specialist Task Force 551 MEC Testing Framework concluded in Apr 2019.

In all these consultancies, Nextworks team has worked as member of the Expert Team and in some cases covered also the role of STF leader, which demonstrates the level of trustiness gained with ETSI and competence in running these types of professional activities.

In addition, the exploitation of the 5G and NFV/MEC know-how matured also through 5GCity activities has enlarged the work of the company in relation to the 5G trial experimentation in Prato (IT), by OpEn Fiber (the largest fiber optic operator in Italy). The 5G trial in Prato is deploying 5G NR and 5G Core Network by ZTE and runs validation with use cases for eHealth, Industry 4.0, Smart Culture and Smart Mobility. Nextworks' expertise on virtualization and orchestration infrastructure design has matured into private consultancies aiming at producing design recommendations for the edge infrastructures, and Technical Project Management of the overall trial planning.

Thanks to the gained visibility in 5G Community, Nextworks has been also contacted by foreign system integrators and roots for partnerships have been established to contribute towards joint offering of consultancy services on 5G in other nations.

Based on matured team know-how, the consultancy service offering of the Nextworks' Knowledge Division has been restructured during the period to better match market requests. As of today, and thanks to knowledge matured in 5GCity, Nextworks is capable to offer:

- *Expert-level training on 5G, NFV, MEC, SDN architecture and tools*, specifically designed for network and software development professionals
- *Senior SDN/NFV Network Architect*, for consultancies focused on design of SDN/NFV PoCs, virtualized infrastructures (private, public hybrid cloud) and production services
- *Senior SDN/NFV Service Architect*, for consultancies focused on definition of operative procedures for onboarding and acceptance of VNFs, Business Continuity, HA, Disaster Recovery, Test procedures, test plans, test reports
- *Technical project management*, for consultancies focused on design and roll-out of 5G/SDN/NFV projects to help you to deliver complex platforms through coordination of multi-national teams of professionals.
- *Cloud-native IoT solution design and development*, for consultancies focused on development of orchestration and control tools for cloud-native and virtualization environments.

The expected consolidation of 5G Neutral Host platform (joint exploitation) and its validation in Lucca can further open to exploitation opportunities of the project foreground.

In particular, Nextworks is evaluating opportunities for collaboration with other 5GCity partners working in Lucca (CoDi, Comune di Lucca, RAI) to contact together potential stakeholders (e.g. local representatives of Museo Casa Puccini and Teatro del Giglio) to implement Smart Museum and Smart Theatre services with 5G, which can include:

- user-profiled UHD streaming of media contents in the museum or from the theatre
- integration of IoT devices to detect user presence and adjust lighting scenarios (leveraging on Nextworks' IoT product offering)

-
- integration of AR services for augmented touristic experience in some areas of the city (e.g. Piazza Anfiteatro, Museum Puccini, Torre Guinigi, etc.)

Similarly, the advancements matured in Use Case 1 Public Safety applications can offer the opportunity to use the 5GCity Neutral Host platform and some of its Virtual Network Functions for video analytics to implement:

- person identification, flow counting, flow & territory monitoring,
- automatic alerting and request for inspections in case of abuse/misuse of public spaces

The evaluation of the business potential of this area of product offering to municipalities is under evaluation by the Nextworks' Sales Group.

4.1.8. LUCCA

Exploiting 5G communication in the area of city surveillance, especially in relation to possible threats and crimes, is clearly a main area of interest for the City of Lucca, as the mid/sized town is willing to increase the quality of the historic environment and safety for visitors, tourist and its citizen.

5GCITY is providing to the town an extended experience in understanding and managing 5G infrastructures, also useful for the preparation of the design of more effective services the city of Lucca in order to deliver to citizens an increased environment monitoring, higher quality of life and security.

In particular, the project activities of the first period provided higher understanding about the do and don'ts related to:

- Designing better architecture to supply video-surveillance service;
- UHD video distribution together with CODI and RAI
- Set up of 5G networks in city environments, especially for aspects related to environmental electromagnetic pollution and optimization of the radio network devices to be integrated into an existing environment with constrains related to preservation of the local architectural heritage.

In brief the plans of the city of LUCCA for the next period are the following:

- Continuous consolidation of knowledge generated by 5GCity technical and legal topics
- Exploitation of 5GCity project outcomes useful for video surveillance and 5G network set up optimization, as above described.

Eventually, it became recently more and more interesting for the city to exploit 5G to boost access to contents for tourism and therefore the provision of immersive services and its applications, primarily targeted for tourists and visitor.

4.1.9. Italtel

Considering what already reported in deliverable D6.3, during the second year of the project Italtel put a strong attention to the progress of 5G specifications and developments, being 5G a perfect unifying framework for present and future applications. 5G adoption enables improving current operation and business position in existing markets, and enables the expansion in new markets in which to secure a strong leadership position. Furthermore, the Multi Access Edge Computing (ETSI MEC) technology adoption, allows the migration of a number of functions, services and content from the core network to the mobile edge network.

In this scenario, Italtel R&D worked in the extension of the product portfolio considering two main topics:

- Development of a proprietary MEC platform in order to host MEC applications

-
- Development/Adaptation of Media management applications (i.e. Real time video streaming and transcoding, Immersive Video Services in crowded events, Video analytics, Augmented Reality) to run in the MEC environment.

The participation to 5GCity is boosting Italtel capacity to bring virtualization and cloudification paradigm to the extreme edge of the network leveraging 5G and MEC, enabling development and deployment of new applications for emerging markets and verticals.

4.1.10. Barcelona – IMI

As a public administration, Institut Municipal d'Informàtica (IMI) will exploit the results of the project to plan 5G network Deployment over urban furniture, impulse new public services and explore improvements in the existing ones. Thanks to the knowledge generated during the project and the pilot conducted in Barcelona, IMI will have the opportunity to test new ways of using 5G technology to improve the safety in the city and get information on the opportunities this technology offers in other sectors. The information and experience gathered during the project will be useful to inspire and provide orientation to future trials with 5G technology in the city, using the public results of the 5GCITY project to improve the innovations generated and tested in the city and ease the participation of IMI and local companies in those trials. In this domain, the project will contribute to the digitalisation and generation of opportunities for the local companies working in this domain, helping them to become more competitive thanks to the learnings of the pilots conducted in 5GCITY when conducting pilots in the area. 5GCITY will also contribute to generate in-house knowledge and provide first-hand experience on the state of the art of 5G technologies and their actual functioning. The project results will hence be useful to improve the institution efficiency on decision-making and set a benchmark of current technologies and their potential in the domains tested.

Delivering on the 5G promise of increased data rates, and ubiquitous coverages, poses stringent requirements on traditional vertically integrated operators. In particular, telecom operators are expected to massively roll out Small Cells, which requires finding appropriate urban spaces with both backhaul and energy availability. Network sharing becomes essential to unlock those commercial massive deployments. The open access model, or neutral host, will come to play a key role on the deployment of 5G networks, especially in urban scenarios where very dense Small Cell deployments are required.

5GCity focuses on how common smart city infrastructure (i.e. small cells and processing power at the very edge of networks) can bring benefit to municipalities based on resource sharing and end-to-end virtualization, pushing the cloud model to the extreme edge. 5GCity will design, develop, deploy and demonstrate a distributed cloud and radio platform for municipalities and infrastructure owners acting as 5G neutral hosts.

5GCITY concept joined with Public Neutral Operator concept became a new paradigm for 5G infrastructure Deployment in cities. The Barcelona Digital City Plan aims to progressively provide all areas of the city with infrastructures, resources, incentives and programmes so that each community, neighbourhood and district has access to the resources that allow citizens, of all ages and statuses, to use technology ensuring better public services and a more balanced and sustainable economic and social growth. By that, Neutral host a Neutral Operator concepts applied in Macroblock Barcelona Urban Model must be a basis for Barcelona Digital City Plan.

4.1.11. betevé

betevé is the local broadcast TV company of the city of Barcelona including also a FM radioweb and social networks content provider. To accomplish with our duty, we use all kind of technologies. In the past we have used satellite technology to make live connections but it has different disadvantages. Price is very high for a local TV station, schedule has to be done in advance, municipal permission is needed to park the small DSNG (Digital Satellite News Gathering) unit in the street near the place where the event you are interested in is going to take place...

Some years ago betevé substituted this technology for 4G technology, using what is called a “BackPack”, that is basically a small computer battery operated, with a software to compress the TV signal and another software to split the signal 8bonding in as many parts as modems you are using to send the signal. Normally we are using up to 6 modems from 3 different operators to guaranty the connection. This technology works very well in favourable conditions the connection cannot be guaranteed to the network nor the required BW to send the signal.

5GCity project can give solutions to the actual transmission problems:

- Priority of connection to the network, due to the slice assignment.
- Guaranteed BW, implied to the slice definition

The plans for **betevé** in the project and up to the end of it, is test the network deployed to perform the experiments, in 22@ testbed and also in the new location that will be deployed in the city hall.

betevé will also try to go one step further integrating a virtual production system in the edge, either from an independent company to the project, or looking for synergies with other members of the consortium like MOG and try to integrate their UC with the **betevé** one.

4.1.12. MOG

MOG Technologies is a technology provider, developing solutions (hardware and software) to enable different types of media workflows. Despite its strong presence in the broadcasting area (SONY, ADOBE, AVID, Al-Jazeera, Disney, HBO, Apple, BBC, RTVE and FOX are among its clients), in more than 40 countries, using cloud computing and state of the art telecommunications technologies like 5G for the professional media sector is relatively new for MOG. In the broadcasting sector, MOG will use the developments from 5GCITY to target broadcasters and media production companies (e.g. newspapers) and similar organizations. Event organizers, like municipalities or cultural/sports associations are also another important target marketing group for the company as they can use the application to cover events lease the equipment (cameras, cables, etc.) from MOG and use the virtual newsroom application to deliver a high quality personalized edited video to a large number of users. It’s important to note that MOG’s strategic alliance with Level 3 Communications, a major global cloud provider, will facilitate MOG’s market penetration, in this specific segment, and the creation of new business opportunities.

Therefore, the company intends to develop a novel marketing strategy for this new area, which includes participation as an exhibitor in the most relevant trade fairs like IBC, NAB and WEB Summit and a strong web presence. Main competitors in the broadcasting industry are AVID, which has a strong presence in professional editing, or Anvato that has a technology capable of live streaming events and cloud production. However, the market still does not offer a solution capable off seamless editing on the fly through a multiplayer interface several broadcast high quality feeds; and, this solution coming out of 5GCITY could be further combined with those of AVID or ANVATO, having a multiplier effect.

MOG is mainly a product-oriented company, thus the developments of 5GCITY will be incorporated in existing products (ingest line) as innovative new features or be used to increase the company portfolio and then sold/licensed. MOG will also be able to provide and sell training and consultancy services to the set of clients described above that need to increase the visibility of a brand or increase their actual sources of revenues.

During the second year, MOG continued the exploitation activities of the first year. At the same time, it further developed the crowd-system ecosystem necessary to implement and deploy the use case in the 5G City framework. During this year, MOG has carried on with the following activities

- Identification of key stakeholders and target groups for exploiting the UC results. These were more elaborately detailed in D2.4 and include: a) Worldwide event organizers who need to create new experiences in their events b) broadcasters, media groups and media production companies who need to reduce their live event production costs c) media integrators who can use the crowd

streaming ecosystem for projects with final clients and d) sport clubs who want to use the ecosystem to engage their fans in matches.

- Associated with the stakeholders listing, the proper exploitation channels were highlighted: a) 5GCity partners interested in this use case will use their salesforce who will promote the ecosystem through direct contact, b) sectorial relevant industrial fairs, such as NAB or IBC can be used to present the ecosystem to a large diversity of key market stakeholders, c) social media using specific campaigns and platforms, d) in Academic Conferences enhancing the innovative project components to validate the product as a scientific breakthrough e) presence in the media (newspaper, radio, TV) through the preparation of specific press releases and f) in Standardization forums such as SMPTE, AMWA or others showcasing the ecosystem interoperability features
- Continue the work regarding market surveillance and analysis further detailed in D6.4. According to Price Waterhouse Coopers report “Perspectives from the Global Entertainment & Media Outlook 2018–2022”, indicates that the entertainment market, which television, film and video production accounts for a significant share will steadily grow 4,4% until 2022. Consumers are expected to spend more time engaging in Entertainment and Media with an increase of 25,4% in data consumption related to video until 2022. According to Deloitte, in 2018, video and audio will generate 89% of this year’s consumer Internet data traffic. eMarketer forecasts that the number of people who normally watch digital video at least once a month in the U.S. will reach 248.9 million by 2022, up from 228.8 million this year. People ask for information and recommendations to other people in early infancy and the same process is repeated until they die. Throughout the ages, governments, public entities and private business have been used, with great success, to tackle different types of challenges. As an example, in the 19th century, James Murray, a British philosopher asked his readers to send him different references to different types of words. The challenge had a great success with a huge number of respondents and was used as the initial base for the Oxford English Dictionary. Nowadays, Wikipedia is one of the most famous examples of crowd’s power, an online encyclopedia, edited by more or less anonymous users throughout the world. The power crowd sourcing for different areas (crowd-solving, crowd-voting, crowdfunding...) is been recognized as a major driver of innovation. In 2016, crowdfunding platforms added up to a total of \$34.4 billion dollars, with crowdsourcing being a key enabler of freelance business. A 2012 survey from Crowdsourcing.org indicates that there are different ways to engage crowds, namely through crowd creative applications such as the one connected with the use case. It is expected that, in 2020, users will spend 65 minutes per day watching videos, accounting for 22% of the total time. At the same time, online video and advertising will grow significantly, when compared to other traditional media channels such as TV or newspapers.
- Further research, namely by fostering the creation of related MSc and PhD thesis and the design of new R&D projects. During this year, MOG has been awarded with the H2020 ICT ARTICONF project. This is a project; which main goal is to develop a tool bench for creating democratic decentralized social networks. In it, MOG will further develop the crowd-streaming ecosystem to support blockchain based transactions, introducing a rewarding mechanism for content producers.
- Analysed and studied potential IPR measures that can be applied to 5GCity results. In this particular axis, exploitable results were identified and matched with potential IPR mechanisms. So far, the conclusions were to use secret know-how as the main method of IP protection. A deeper and extensive study will be carried during the upcoming period.
- MOG continued to develop the use case components in order to scale up their TRL. During this year, a version of the system was presented in ICT 2018 and the 2019 Mobile World Congress.

Identify possible third parties that can benefit from the project results. During this year, MOG has further developed its partnership with Level 3 Communications so that the later can host the crowd-streaming platform. An experimental trial of the use case was also made with the support of Jornal de Notícias. Jornal de Notícias is one of the largest Portuguese newspaper and a potential user/client of the project results.

During the final period, MOG will continue to exploit the results of developing the use case components in connection with the 5G City ecosystem. It will conclude the developments and test them in real life scenarios and project the prototype sustainability after the project lifespan. Namely, MOG will:

- a) Create the final business case for the crowd streaming ecosystem
- b) Conclude the market surveillance study, in order to evaluate trends, countries, business models and sectors of application
- c) Promote the creation of derived R&D, namely by identifying individual and/or collaborative R&D projects in which it can participate
- d) Finish analysing the most suitable IPR measures to protect the 5G City findings.
- e) Test the prototype in real life scenarios in two cities (Barcelona and Bristol)
- f) Finish the identification of third parties who can serve as initial beta testers of the prototype
- g) Define a sustainability plan for the crowd-streaming ecosystem after the conclusion of 5GCity

4.1.13. RAI

RAI Radiotelevisione Italiana, the Italian Public Service Broadcaster and Italy's largest radio-television broadcasting company, has played a major role in shaping the country's life and customs over the last decades. RAI started broadcasting its radio programmes in 1924 and nowadays broadcasts over 32.000 hours of television programmes (of which 75% are produced in-house) and 52.000 hours of radio programmes per year. Rai boasts national and international reach, high quality signal, and coverage of the country's total area and reach of the Italian communities' world-wide. It is currently present on terrestrial and satellite digital platforms with 13 TV channels, most of them also available in High Definition. Moreover, its presence on the Web (<http://www.raisplay.it>) includes 14 live TV channels, 10 radio channels, web-TV thematic channels plus over one thousand on-demand programmes and more than 450 hours monthly published on-demand, targeting PCs, mobile devices (smartphones, tablets) and connected TVs.

For RAI, project results will be mainly constituted by the results of the experimental network pilots, in order to gain knowledge about new features offered by 5G technology in the areas of interest of a media company. RAI will exploit project results in two different areas, the final user area to enrich the television experience and in the television production area to use the new network to facilitate the covering of events, exploiting 5G features by providing new services: from audio/video UHD video distribution also as 360° video experience up to the virtual/augmented/mixed reality for immersive services. In particular:

- Knowledge in IP-end-to-end highly distributed broadcast production workflow, cloud/edge-based video and audio encoding, mixed reality for improved TV entertainment
- New TV formats enabled by new features offered by the 5GCity technologies
- Integration of the media company production workflow with new distributed edge network and computing technologies.

In particular RAI is collaborating with other partners of the project for the creation of state of the art television products in order to exploit 5GCity technologies in the area of the television production and in the area of distribution, taking into account UHD content and Immersive experiences in relevant cities. In this environment a particular focus of exploitation activities for RAI is about:

- OTT services in the 5G era.
- Cultural heritage for touristic and museums services.

4.1.14. INCITES

INCITES Consulting SARL is taking advantage of 5GCity project to enhance its knowledge, future market reports and seminars related to 5G networks that will be deployed in future Cities with specific focus on business cases and commercial opportunities via advanced innovative use cases.

More specifically the involvement at 5GCity will give INCITES the opportunity to:

- Enhance its future market reports and seminars related to 5G networks with specific focus on new business cases and opportunities arising from the model of the Neutral Host.
- Exploit new business models regarding 5G networking and provide a technical competitive edge in the drafting of the regulatory frameworks for the future digital service economy.
- Provide consulting services to operators regarding the future deployment of 5G networks, cost charging mechanisms and sharing schemes using the neutral host model.
- Will be able to perform techno-economic analysis for future investment plans that include various type of technologies and architectures.
- Strengthen INCITES Consulting SARL position as the reference international center of excellence for 5G networking

In details, during the second year of 5GCity, INCITES had the opportunity to conduct a survey (as part of MWC19) in order to understand operators' concerns about the NH model and other issues like spectrum ownership, regulatory considerations, the role of municipalities etc. The analysis of the collected questionnaires provided INCITES with all the necessary details in order to help its clients to make informed decisions. Moreover, INCITES was leading business modelling and regulatory considerations activities giving it the opportunity to investigate the value proposition and charging schemes of the 5GCity NH model. The gained knowledge allowed INCITES to enhance the Luxembourg's 5G strategy report with both the NH and the edge computing concepts as well as to propose the necessary regulatory intervention.

Luxembourg 5G Strategy

Expert Report

September 2018

Created by:

INCITES
Consulting SARL

 THE GOVERNMENT
OF THE GRAND DUCHY OF LUXEMBOURG
Ministry of State
Department of Media, Telecommunications
and Digital Policy

During the final period, INC will continue to exploit the results of developing the 5GCITY Business case. It will develop the techno-economic model in order to investigate the viability of a potential investment. In details, INC will:

- Develop a demand model
- Develop a dimensioning model
- Estimate CAPEX and OPEX
- Define a charging scheme
- Estimate the revenues
- Calculate the necessary cash flows and financial indices

4.1.15. WIND3

WIND3 is the leading operator in the Italian mobile market, with more than 30 million customers and a market share above 37% for the mobile access. Wind Tre is achieving significant efficiencies and important investments in digital infrastructures. The move towards LTE and LTE-A has been carried out in all the geographic areas where such generations of cellular system were required according to service demand.

5GCity architecture is designed to be compliant to a wide range of use cases according to the fulfilled requirements, especially in terms of latency, resilience, coverage, and bandwidth. One of the challenges is to provide end-to-end network and cloud infrastructure slices over the same physical infrastructure to meet vertical-specific requirements as well as mobile broadband services in parallel. 5GCity has identified three main scenarios which groups the project Use Cases, namely the Neutral Host, Industry vertical (Media and Entertainment) and city services.

In the first scenario (Neutral Host), 5GCity leverages its virtualization platform to enable the cities (or any infrastructure provider) to create dynamic end-to-end slices containing both virtualized edge and network resources and lease it to third-party operators or verticals. The scenario consists of managing the underlying physical infrastructure to offer a set of virtual resources to an operator, who builds, on top, its own services ready for end-user consumption.

The second scenario (Industry vertical) is strictly related to different aspects of the media and entertainment industry, which are strictly integrated into 5GCity project, and encompass all the Use Cases pivoting around video acquisition, editing and delivery.

The third scenario is related to Smart City which is tailored to the specific needs of a city (WindTre is focusing on the city of Lucca).

Concerning the second scenario, immersive experience with high quality video (HD or UHD videos) for tourists, including 3D video, 360 degree video, Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) applications, can be considered. The third scenario exploits the cities' surveillance cameras by deploying a virtualized monitoring service that can process video streams near cameras automatically to identify illegal dumping, and for autonomous mobility in the city to enhance public transportation. Of course, the first scenario is a profitable enabler for all the use-cases belonging to the families of the first and second scenarios.

4.1.16. Accelleran

Accelleran exploitation strategy is based around the following pillars:

- Evolution and enhancement of the disaggregation of the Small Cell software components and the virtualisation of vRAN Control Plane (L3 Control Plane) in the context of the 5GCity virtualisation
- Enablement of the local breakout of the user plane at the Edge/MEC server in the context of the use cases needing Edge/MEC functionality

- Enhancements of multi-operator neutral-host capabilities using standard 4G 3GPP functionality and upcoming 5G-based slicing technologies
- Integration into 5GCity orchestrating platform
- Use of these enhancements in future projects and the exploitation of Accelleran flexible RAN/vRAN software solutions product proposition and the availability of Small Cell products leveraging on those

Accelleran has already been showing neutral host demos in different events along the lines of the use of Small Cell solutions for Neutral Hosts and private LTE networks (Mobile World Congress Barcelona 2018, CBRS Annual Members Meeting Washington 2018, Small Cell World Summit London 2018) in 3-layer architectures with virtualisation of small cell components running in edge servers.

Accelleran has defined NETCONF model for virtualisation of the Small Cell aligned with i2CAT model for WiFi APs. This model is being used to enable the control and management of the Small Cell from the SDN controller.

These technologies are being delivered and tried in the city pilots in Barcelona, Bristol and Lucca and will be used as pilot trials and showcases for other RAN/vRAN products supporting distributed cloud radio platforms to enable neutral host 5G smart city projects.

These technologies are feeding directly into the commercialisation of Accelleran Small Cell solutions and products. One important example of this is the official launch during MWC2019 of the Accelleran dRAX™ Open Interface RAN Intelligence virtual RAN solution which delivers a true multi-vendor, disaggregated and virtualised RAN Intelligent Control Plane as per ORAN. This Cloud Native solution managed and orchestrated through Kubernetes (containers) or OpenStack (VMs) supports key 5G paradigms and enables true scalability and interoperability with carrier and mission critical grade software quality (MISRA). One of the key reference use cases for Accelleran dRAX virtualised RAN solution as indicated in the dRAX™ product brief is the 5GCity project, where Accelleran Small Cells and vRAN components are being used to enable the 5GCity city pilots and 5G neutral host technologies (http://www.accelleran.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Accelleran_DS_dRAX.pdf).

Product Brief

dRAX™ Open Interface RAN Intelligence

dRAX™ Case Studies
 ONF M-CORD M-CORD from ONF uses dRAX™ components in their Telco Edge Cloud reference implementation. dRAX™ Control Plane is used as virtualised control plane together with E1000 radio units. dRAX™ is deployed as a set of Docker containers within the CORD service mesh interworking with the rest of the CORD infrastructure.

5G CITY
 5G City is an H2020 R&D programme with support from the European Union to provide a Cloud and Distributed Radio Platform for 5G Neutral Hosts (such as municipalities) to deploy virtual networks supporting multi-tenancy through dynamic end-to-end slice management and virtualisation. The cities of Barcelona, Bristol and Lucca are hosting real-world trials of the technology which uses dRAX™ to implement the RAN component.

The diagram shows a layered architecture. At the top is the **Control Plane** containing the **dRAX™ Intelligent RAN Controller** and **dRAX™ data Bus**. Below this are **Cell Control Plane** components (P1, P1, V1) which interface with **Cell** and **Microcell Sites**. The **User Plane** includes **Control Sites** (RAN, MEC Apps) and **Control Plane Open Interfaces** (E1, E2). The architecture is supported by **Orchestrated Cloud Automation** (Openstack, Kubernetes) and **Control Sites** (RAN, MEC Apps).

PRODUCT DESCRIPTION

Accelleran dRAX™ delivers a true multi-vendor, disaggregated and virtualised RAN Intelligent Control Plane as per ORAN.

Key features of dRAX™ are:

- **Cloud Native**
 All dRAX™ components are lightweight containers communicating over a common messaging bus.
- **ORAN Compliance**
 Accelleran is a proud and active member of the ORAN Alliance. We support this overdue initiative and dRAX™ architecture is compliant with the ORAN approach.
- **Containers (Kubernetes)/VM(OpenStack)**
 dRAX™ containers/VMs are managed and orchestrated through Kubernetes/Openstack respectively.
- **Control User Plane Separation (CUPS)**
 dRAX™ was conceived and designed to be cloud native. The dRAX™ control plane is field proven in our range of embedded small cells and fully interoperable with our own User Plane implementations or other vendors INIC implementation.
- **User Plane Location Independence**
 Control and User Plane location are independent and flexible. User Plane processing can be independently assigned per UE and per Service Bearer, opening up huge flexibility for intelligent resource assignment and efficient MEC access.

4G LTE and 5G
 The development of 5G NR opens exciting opportunities for the future, but we also believe that 4G LTE has a lot more to offer. That's why dRAX™ also support LTE technology to enable the benefits of Cloud Native vRAN in networks of today as well as tomorrow.

- **Open Integration**
 Thanks to the dRAX™ open APIs and convergence libraries, any radio head or small cell platform can be integrated into a dRAX™ network.
- **Scalable**
 dRAX™ can be implemented on a single microserver for the smallest edge cloud. At the other end of the scale, clusters of hundreds of cells can be supported with either native user plane processing on x86 or user plane offload to GPU or dedicated INIC.
- **Mission Critical Reliability**
 All dRAX™ code is written to Accelleran's unique set of SW development standards such as MISRA which are based on established practices from safety critical industries.

4.1.17. Comunicare Digitale

Comunicare Digitale APS – CoDi, with its twenty years' experience in the organization and promotion of new digital technologies for the media and broadcasting industry, participating at the 5GCity project has substantially increase its knowledge on the 5G networks, study its future markets, and best practices for the promotion of 5G services, new business, and commercial opportunities.

For the time being, it has analysed and promote important events participation, organizing conference, seminars and hackathon related to 5G ecosystem. In prevision, once the project will be over, it is taking in serious consideration the creation and organization of **ad hoc event** that will gather all together the three cities involved in the project: Barcelona, Bristol and Lucca and create a **5GCity Smart Cities Summit**, that will include also other European and worldwide cities involved in the 5G revolution. CoDi will in this way promote liaison activities between all the cities that will activate 5G services and establish commercial opportunities in Europe and abroad. Networking is a "focus goal" to connect and act in Europe; so CoDi will continue to enlarge and strengthen the 5G audience with professionals, companies, associations, stockholders, institutions, public and private entities.

As expressed in previous deliverables, CoDi's involvement in 5GCity project is more than ever giving the opportunity to:

- Deeper its future market liaison and networking opportunities in the 5G ecosystem, between operators, companies, research and European institutions. Cooperation between the various subjects embodies the principle of the European Union. A strong collaboration between them is strongly sought; both to open new collaborative projects, to strengthen efforts on research, and to cooperate in a concrete way to be more effective and obtain higher results;
- Creating new promotion and communication opportunities for those business models that will be active in the 5G networking; among the media and entertainment industry. While waiting for the 5G to have important effects on IoT, on the development of Smart Cities, automotive safety, applications on tourism and health. The media represents the first front runner of the development of this new technology, thanks to an "immersive experience", with 4K / UHD and 360°. What it is called the "NGX" (new generation experience) is what CoDi wants to promote and is already talking about with all European industry. In this sense, with its direct involvement in 5GCity project, and for the lucky coincidence of related events going on in Lucca, and for the history of the demos that have made Lucca visible to the main stakeholders, the proposal is carried forward with important results and appreciations from important organizations; such as HD Forum Italia, DPP, Ultra HD Forum;
- Providing consulting services and marketing analysis for future investment plans; for a communication competitive edge in the future digital economy; on new business arising from the video acquisition and production, UHD video distribution, immersive services use cases. Driving the next processes, not only at the level of technology, but also supporting and adjusting future scenarios on the verticals, is also essential to create the conditions for a successful European industry in a highly competitive sector. A sector that today sees large companies as protagonists, predominantly based in the United States. The help that must be given to the important European creative industry, it also passes through 5G deployment. Throughout the extraordinary European "open-air library"; the important historic and cultural heritage of each country member; the industry that can speak with only one language in the agri-food, environment, and architecture sectors, it is possible to change and have a European edge to support a global market. In this sense, the video, the quality of distribution and the involvement of a wider audience can create great benefits;
- Strengthening Comunicare Digitale APS international position as the promotion, communication, and networking reference for the excellence of 5G European networking. The convinced mission of evangelization has always been the principal activity of CoDi. It was with DVBT, with DVBSH, with 4K/UHD, 8K, 3D, and today with 5G, also for a holistic view of the connection system. The various

activities carried out in the first year have had the incipit of including and widening the various sectors of civil society, industry, and institutions.

CoDi has played a circular role in the various activities carried out in the project and in favour of 5G. Events, workshops, meetings, seminars, communication, information, production were the pillars of the various activities that took place in the main European cities, as evidenced of the relevant activity carried out at all levels. An involvement that has been reverberated to create the best conditions of interest and favour towards 5G.

For the first time, a RAI 360° production was made at **Puccini's House Museum** to verify a series of expected results: quality production, network transport, and mobile devices, immersive involvement of the public, and interaction between them. The production was showcased during the **Lucca Comics and Games 2018** edition, an event that sees and involves many millennials. An audience attentive to technologies and new languages. Taking advantage of a high-level production; a "European" content well known all over the world; a 'brand' widely recognized as Puccini's operas and famous arias - the whole Metropolitan Opera of New York playbill is composed of European creative plays; in conclusion, a unique European content.

The growth of interest in 5G will be stimulated, as well as, the applications made for the market, to create an environment ready to exploit the capabilities and peculiarities at European level. Strong collaborations will always be sought, in the logic of strengthening the proposal and guaranteeing the best possible offering, also for the purposes of industrial, institutional, and civil applications.

Maintaining and reinforcing important actions in information, dissemination, promotion and visibility of the various activities are fundamental in this last part of the 5G project for a successful 5G experience in Europe.

4.1.18. UbiWhere

Ubiwhere aims at providing 5G technologies and solutions as well as capitalising their appearance with innovative Smart City solutions. Ubiwhere's long-term vision is to provide solutions that merge the main outcomes of both its TELCO (Telecom and Future Internet) and Smart City sectors. As such, most recently, Ubiwhere has partnered with other two major Portuguese entities (Metalgalva and PROEF Group) to develop Smart Lamppost (<http://smartlamppost.com>): a modular concept of a lamppost with bleeding edge technology, allowing municipalities to future-proof their Smart City and Mobile Network Operators to cost-effectively rollout 5G solutions. Aligned with 5GPPP's indicative predictions regarding future 5G network deployments dependency on a five to ten-fold rollout increase of antennas and small cells, Smart Lamppost's is betting on the benefits of the novel neutral host approach to tackling such scalability hurdles, offering Municipalities the chance to become new Tower Companies, in this new era of cellular technology. Therefore, and aligned with the project's goal of designing and developing a full-fledge cloud and radio platform for 5G-based services deployments, it is the Company's objective to exploit the 5GCity project as much as possible, as to (i) validate Smart Lamppost's core business model amongst relevant stakeholders (Infrastructure Owners, Network Operators, Service Providers and Software Developers) (ii) advance its state-of-the-art regarding neutral hosting and network slicing and (iii) design an easy-to-use web platform, for all these different stakeholders, with a clean and effective user experience. Due to this close link between 5GCity's neutral host paradigm and Smart Lamppost's as a 5G-enabler, Ubiwhere hopes to leverage key components of 5GCity's platform and include them in its commercial product that is Smart Lamppost. Also importantly is Ubiwhere's recent take on V2X, through Unicle (<http://unicle.io>): It is the Company's goal to exploit the proposed Use Case #6, CCAM, to accelerate its developments and time to market.

Ubiwhere has been designing 5GCity's web SDK and platform, the two fundamental software components which connect the different underlying services of 5GCity's Platform, ultimately allowing, in essence, Service Providers to (i) design network services, (ii) ask for network slices and, finally, (iii) instantiate such services across the slice. The web platform is, thus, enabling the usage of a real Cloud Edge and Radio Platform for

Neutral Hosts and Service Providers. The efforts towards such developments have been broadly disseminated by demoing its capabilities in numerous relevant where the company had its own stand such as Smart City Expo World Congress 2018 and IoT-Week, both in 2018, and also EuCNC 2018 and Mobile World Congress 2019, representing 5GCity. The findings and developments of these web platforms are crucial for Smart Lamppost's long-term product roadmap as the objectives of said project are closely aligned with that of 5GCity's, by enabling Municipalities and other interested-parties to act as new Tower Companies, leveraging Smart Lampposts' web marketplace.

4.2. Joint Exploitation Plans/Activities

Due to the large number of partners in this project, and the focus on different use cases distributed across different countries, it has been agreed that joint exploitation plans shall be designed using dedicated hubs. Those hubs must concentrate the efforts of some partners, making a much more efficient usage of the resources and applying specific knowledge to concrete plans.

The described hubs have been created in the same locations 5GCity project is running, so 3 different hubs are going to exploit jointly the outcomes of 5GCity. These joint exploitation hubs will cover the infrastructure/platform itself and specific/dedicated scenarios that can be exploited in order to monetize the platform.

In this way, during this section we will describe the following joint exploitation plans:

- In the Barcelona hub, the *"E2E Multi-carrier NH platform deployment and commercialization"* and *"Video acquisition service using dedicated slices of the NH infrastructure"* plans.
- In the Lucca hub, the *"Immersive Video Services for Smart Cities"* plan.
- In the Bristol hub, the *"(360) Video content distribution in real time"* plan.

4.2.1. Barcelona Hub Joint Exploitation Plan

4.2.1.1. E2E Multi-carrier NH platform deployment and commercialization

As part of the Neutral Host (NH) model described and analysed in the project, the infrastructure deployment and commercialization is the basis for any future revenue generation based on the multiple possible use cases.

This scenario plans to describe how to carry out the commercial exploitation of the NH platform deployment by **i2CAT**, **Cellnex**, **VOSYS** and **Accelleran**, with business model contribution from **Incites**, and **IMI** as end customer. In the following points it is described the expected participation and/or point of view from each partner.

a) i2CAT

Apart from its individual exploitation strategy (c.f. Section 4.1.1), i2CAT plans to exploit the results of 5GCity project jointly with other consortium partners as well. The 5GCity platform allows an ICT infrastructure owner to manage, slice and offer their infrastructure to multiple tenants temporarily at the same time. As mentioned earlier, being the lead developer of the 5GCity platform, i2CAT recognizes 5GCity platform as an asset for the organization. i2CAT intends to work along with infrastructure owners such as Cellnex and IMI to further develop the 5GCity platform to add customized features to suit different infrastructure scenarios and to integrate their existing OSS/BSS with 5GCity platform to facilitate the transition towards the neutral host. Similarly, the joint effort with Accelleran to integrate their radio technology with the i2CAT RAN controller serves as an enabler for future integrations with new hardware or any new features that may need to be integrated with the controller. This joint exploitation will serve i2CAT as the technology developer to enhance its expertise near to commercial solutions whereas it allows quick access and transition to latest 5G technology solutions for the ICT infrastructure owners.

b) Cellnex

Exploitation activities in Cellnex include joint activities with the 5GCity partners, oriented to the specific infrastructure and platform that is under development.

On top of the basic infrastructure components that Cellnex is going to commercialize individually, the joint solution created to define a Neutral Host infrastructure is a product that creates a new business model.

This new business model is to be offered as-is to the different municipalities working in this project, with special focus in Barcelona, as Cellnex is based in this city. This solution is also expected to be jointly offered to Lucca and potentially to Bristol, although this last one is not participating actively in the project from the City Council point of view.

Once this joint proposition can demonstrate its commercial viability, it is also expected from Cellnex point of view that similar propositions can be offered to other Cities in Europe, in order to support the Neutral Host concept in urban environments.

c) VOSYS

The VOSYS exploitation activity in 5GCity aims at building a vertical VIM-NFVI product solution which enables trusted computing and mixed criticality features in 5G networks. Such product is VOSYS TrustedVIM (<http://www.virtualopensystems.com/en/products/vosystrustedvim/>), developed as a result of 5GCity and derived directly from the 5GCity EdgeVIM component. With TrustedVIM, VOSYS ambitions to secure the safety critical part of the 5G infrastructure, thus addressing the emerging market of 5G security (including verticals like Industrial, IoT, Connected Vehicles, healthcare, etc).

d) Accelleran

Accelleran plans to carry commercial exploitation of the following provided 5GCity components of the 5GCity platform infrastructure:

- Physical Small Cell product equipment (Hardware)
- Virtual dRAX RAN Control Plane intelligence product (Software)

With regards to the physical Small Cell product equipment, Accelleran would make commercial exploitation through the usual traditional revenue streams applied by infrastructure vendors, mainly:

- Physical Small Cell product equipment sales (CAPEX)
- Support and Maintenance contracts with neutral hosts (OPEX)

With regards to the virtual dRAX RAN Control Plane intelligence, the virtualisation and disaggregation of the RAN network components will bring new revenue streams paradigms (new in the RAN) similar to the software royalties of other software industries:

- Virtual dRAX RAN Control plane intelligence software product royalties (bundled with physical Small Cell product equipment sales or separate if the software runs managing compatible physical Small Cell products delivered by third party vendors)

Beyond these traditional and virtualised software revenues streams, Accelleran is willing to explore new paradigms (yet to be defined) whereby certain revenue streams could be linked to the added value services and use cases delivered over the infrastructure. This could be, as example, a percentage of the total revenue generated by these services/use cases provided to end users.

e) Incites

Incites is eager to participate in this joint exploitation activity by defining the appropriate business models, based on the ones described in this project, and supporting all the business coordination in any future commercial agreement.

f) IMI

As the representative of the City of Barcelona, IMI plays a “customer” or “end user” role in this joint exploitation proposal. It shall be included in the *Barcelona Digital City Plan* in order to define the right ways to monetize this proposal, and the best way to offer public services with this solution.

g) Summary of the proposal

All the infrastructure elements combined in the 5GCity architecture creates a solution that can be used by Mobile operators and service providers to offer added-value services to end users. It's in the aim of the consortium partners participating in the 5GCity project, to make this infrastructure a full commercial solution, that can be offered to City Councils to be used both for providing public services to their citizens, and for other private services that can help to monetize public assets.

In this line, Barcelona becomes the first City to be offered with this solution, as soon as the final 5GCity solution is ready. Obviously, some components will not be 100% ready to be commercialized (based on open source solutions, which might lack the right support), but the consortium partners expect to continue working on these solutions together with Barcelona council in order to properly define the right final solution.

The participants in this joint proposal, i2CAT, Cellnex, VOSYS, Accelleran, Incites and IMI, will contribute with different pieces of the architecture, either software, hardware, radio access points, infrastructure, business modelling, or user experience definition, as they have described.

In order to exploit this platform, and after the final solution is ready, it will be necessary to define the services that can host. Those services will be the basis to monetize the solution, no matter if it is also used for public services (e.g. non-profitable) on top of it.

And this is the reason that each hub for joint exploitation has defined one *reference* service that will work as a basis / example to work with, and that will be described in the next sections.

4.2.1.2. Video acquisition service using dedicated slices of the NH infrastructure

Once the E2E Multi-carrier NH platform has been deployed in one metropolitan area, different use cases and scenarios can be setup on top of it in order to provide services to the citizens and to monetize it.

In Barcelona, one of the more promising scenarios for such commercialization is based on the video acquisition services. This joint exploitation is planned to be done by **BTV, Mog, Ubiwhere, IMI** and **Cellnex**, with also business model contribution from **Incites**. In the following points it is described the expected participation and/or point of view from each partner.

a) betevé (BTV)

betevé will make use of the 5GCity technology developed and deployed in the city to develop his normal business and obligations as a public TV station to give the city news and produce city programs of different kind of events, cultural, sports, etc.

To do this betevé intends to use the 5GCity network to make live news transmissions from anywhere in the city where the network should be deployed, gaining in agility, spontaneity and improving the public information service.

betevé also plans to produce live multi-camera events by making use of the 5GCity network, and the MEC infrastructure associated to it to deploy virtual production centres where are needed, improving again the public service obligation that has with the city, by producing live shows with a reduced crew and a high capacity to react in front of an unexpected event.

b) Mog

MOG has developed the crowd streaming platform to be used primarily for the coverage of live events such as music festivals or sports events but, in fact, the same technology can be used to cover different types of news. The crowd streaming ecosystem could accommodate a mix of professional journalists and citizen-based journalism.

MOG can provide the platform to BTV using, for example, a SaaS model. In a breaking news situation such as a terrorist attack or natural disaster, MOG quickly deploys the platform and make it available to BTV. By offering a solution which covers all the content creation process, from capture and streaming of live content through an app to the network infrastructure and the web interface where the editor/director can preview a pre-selected set of video feeds and select one, MOG's ecosystem allows the wide application of crowd journalism by addressing the following main challenges: (i) the need to guarantee a direct, efficient and effective means of communication between journalists and citizens using smartphones and available network infrastructure regardless of the typology and format of the newscast that is intended to be created; (ii) the need to receive, select and process in real-time the different video streams in an elastic way in order to manage different types of crowds and to propagate the edit stream to the TV station so that it can be further distributed in the shortest time possible.

c) Ubiwhere

Ubiwhere has developed 5GCity's front-end components of both Platform and SDK, connecting Service Providers with Neutral Hosts, and effectively creating a user-friendly distributed Edge Cloud and Radio Platform. The SDK front-end component allows Service Providers to design their services which constitutes the final use case to be instantiated under a network slice, using the Web Platform. Thus, the SDK is a must for all 5GCity's Use Case Providers, showcasing how different actors from different verticals may compose and orchestrate their solutions and services using 5G technology in a user-friendly way, from Core to Edge (following the same principles as typical well-known cloud-based platforms). On the other hand, the Web Platform allows Service Providers to bring their business into a Neutral Host environment such as 5GCity. With the latter, services such as MOG's and BTV's system can be properly orchestrated, managed and monitored in a dedicated slice which has been requested via the platform, leveraging Barcelona's (or any other infrastructure) resources.

Thus, Ubiwhere intends to provide all the needed support to ensure Service Providers a smooth operation and great user experience when dealing with 5GCity's distributed edge cloud and radio platform. Furthermore, Ubiwhere is willing to explore and analyse certain and specific functionalities that might be needed from such Service Providers and Admins (Neutral Hosts) of said platforms, which may be, for instance, associated with Billing systems, based on requirements. In the case of Barcelona and the media-related use cases, the Platform will also ensure certain KPIs are being monitored and properly displayed in real-time, as to ensure the level of QoS (Quality of Service) made available to the Service Provider.

d) IMI

As this service is exploiting the assets hosted in Barcelona city, IMI might act potentially as the Facility Manager, providing the needed elements in the public spaces. At the same time, the City of Barcelona will be involved through betevé, which is the public TV service of the Municipality, in the provision of the service.

e) Cellnex

Cellnex plan to play the Neutral Host role in this scenario, thus acting as the entity in charge of the service provision/commercialization to the Service Provider, and operating the platform. No matter which components are to be deployed by different stakeholders, Cellnex would like to play the role of prime contractor, handling the commercial discussions with mobile operators, service providers, venue owners and end customers.

f) Incites

Incites is eager to participate in this joint exploitation activity by defining the appropriate business models, based on the ones described in this project, and supporting all the business coordination in any future commercial agreement.

g) Summary of the proposal

As described in the previous scenario, this joint exploitation plan is based on the infrastructure / platform capabilities provided by 5GCity in the Neutral Host concept.

This particular scenario plans to offer these NH capabilities to one specific service in order to be enjoyed by end users.

As it has been described, the solution proposed by Mog and Ubiwhere can allow betevé, as service provider, to make use of it through the Neutral Host platform, commercialized by Cellnex and following business models proposed by Incites, making use of dedicated assets of Barcelona city.

This service is also potentially exploitable in the other 5GCity locations, and in any other location where the platform (or similar Neutral Host platforms) can be deployed in the future.

4.2.2. Lucca Hub Joint Exploitation Plan

4.2.2.1. Immersive Video Services for Smart Cities

Based on the NH infrastructure expected to be deployed and exploited in Lucca, several scenarios can be used for its commercial exploitation.

In particular, one of the most promising scenarios plans to describe how to provide an immersive experience for tourists using the smart cities capabilities provided by a NH infrastructure. This scenario is expected to be jointly exploited by **Accelleran**, **Nextworks**, **Italtel**, the **Municipality of Lucca**, **RAI**, **WindTre**, **Incites** and **CoDi**. In the following points it is described the expected participation and/or point of view from each partner.

a) Accelleran

Accelleran plans to carry commercial exploitation of the following provided 5GCity components of the 5GCity platform infrastructure:

- Physical Small Cell product equipment (Hardware)
- Virtual dRAX RAN Control Plane intelligence product (Software)

With regards to the physical Small Cell product equipment, Accelleran would make commercial exploitation through the usual traditional revenue streams applied by infrastructure vendors, mainly:

- Physical Small Cell product equipment sales (CAPEX)
- Support and Maintenance contracts with neutral hosts (OPEX)

With regards to the virtual dRAX RAN Control Plane intelligence, the virtualisation and disaggregation of the RAN network components will bring new revenue streams paradigms (new in the RAN) similar to the software royalties of other software industries:

- Virtual dRAX RAN Control plane intelligence software product royalties (bundled with physical Small Cell product equipment sales or separate if the software runs managing compatible physical Small Cell products delivered by third party vendors)

Beyond these traditional and virtualised software revenues streams, Accelleran is willing to explore new paradigms (yet to be defined) whereby certain revenue streams could be linked to the added value services and use cases delivered over the infrastructure. This could be, as example, a percentage of the total revenue generated by these services/use cases provided to end users.

b) Nextworks

The Immersive Video Services for Smart Cities is an interesting application that can complement directly impact on two major business areas of digitalized cities:

- Smart Tourism, particularly critical for Artistic Cities
- Public Safety services

Smart Tourism exploitation opportunities. Lucca's Medieval center has been proposed as an addition to the UNESCO World Heritage List due to the huge amount of monumental and historic wealth. The six historical gates, the pedestrian city walls, many towers, bell towers and monumental Renaissance palaces, Piazza Anfiteatro built on the ruins of the ancient Roman amphitheatre and various museums (e.g. Museo Casa Puccini) compose a significant offering for tourists. In 2018 the city was visited by ca 250k tourist, 58% of which foreigners, with an increasing trend of +3.15% [source Comune di Lucca, Tourism Office].

Moreover, Lucca attracts relevant international large scale public events like Lucca Summer Festival music concerts (<http://www.summer-festival.com/>), Lucca Comics and Games (<https://www.luccacomicsandgames.com/it/lcg/home/>), and Puccini Festival (<https://www.puccinifestival.it/en/>).

In this context, the demand for mixing the cultural offering with innovative digitalized services for the tourist is increasing and mandatory to sustain the positive trend of tourist presences in the city.

In this context, it is of particular interest for Nextworks to build on the service offering capabilities of the 5GCity Neutral Host platform and join forces with other 5GCity stakeholders in Lucca (CoDi, Comune di Lucca, RAI and local representatives of Museo Casa Puccini and Teatro del Giglio) to contribute to implement Smart Museum services which can include

- user-profiled UHD streaming of media contents in the museum
- integration of IoT devices to detect user presence and adjust lighting scenarios (leveraging on Nextworks' IoT product offering)
- integration of AR services for augmented touristic experience in some areas of the city (e.g. Piazza Anfiteatro, Museum Puccini, Torre Guinigi, etc.)

Public Safety exploitation opportunities. Lucca is a Medieval city with a total population of ca 89k individuals [source "[Popolazione Residente al 1° Gennaio 2018](#)". Istat. Retrieved 16 March 2019.] And a density of 480/sq-km. Events like Lucca Comics and Games or Lucca Summer Festival concentrate in a few days up to 250k visitors within the city centre, i.e. with critical impact on public services.

The availability of video analytics services integrated with the 5GCity infrastructure in Lucca and the elastically orchestrated has good potential to represent an important asset to be used by local security forces and municipality to guarantee public safety during the events.

In this context, it is of particular interest for Nextworks to build Public Safety applications offering for cities like Lucca, in which the 5GCity Neutral Host platform and some of its Virtual Network Functions for video analytics can be used to implement

- person identification, flow counting, flow & territory monitoring,
- automatic alerting and request for inspections in case of abuse/misuse of public spaces

For this initiative, key stakeholders are the Comune di Lucca and connected agencies/offices for city security, the public surveillance operation centers, and the event organizers who have to guarantee certain levels of situational monitoring.

Nextworks, as key developer of 5GCity platform technologies configures as 5G/NFV technology provider and can also integrate its IoT service and CCTV offering to enhance the full-chain service capabilities.

c) Italtel

Italtel is putting a strong attention to the 5G specifications and developments, as a perfect unifying framework for present and future applications. 5G is perceived as a possibility to improve current operation and business position in existing markets, and to create new markets in which to secure a strong leadership position. Furthermore, the Multi Access Edge Computing (ETSI MEC) technology adoption, allows the migration of a number of functions, services and content from the core network to the mobile edge network. In this new scenario, IoT, eHealth services, Smart cities and Industry 4.0 solutions are currently driving Italtel

R&D activities. Indeed, Italtel is working on adding new features to Cloud and Edge Cloud applications, already available in its product portfolio for the Telco market, in order to enable a possible expansion towards Smart City market.

In the context of 5GCity, the Use Case “Immersive Video Services for Smart Cities” fits well with Italtel vision for extending its market segments, leveraging the emerging technologies.

In particular, it will allow:

- the extension of the product portfolio that already includes several Media related applications (i.e. Real time video streaming and transcoding, Immersive Video Services in crowded events, Video analytics, Augmented Reality) in the MEC environment (use of MEC platform and compliance with MEC applications requirements)
- the extension of the market segment related to Smart Cities thank to:
 - the adoption of the Neutral Host business model
 - the virtualization of the Smart Cities infrastructure and the 5G connectivity

The Municipality of Lucca, RAI, Wind Tre and all the other partners involved in this Use Case are strong candidates for evaluating a possible joint exploitation of the outcomes of 5GCity, also after the end of the project.

d) Municipality of Lucca

As above described (see section b), the application of Immersive Video Services for Smart Cities can lead to relevant enhancement in the way cultural heritage is perceived by city visitors and tourists, which is something on which the city of Lucca is already working on since many years, including other applications that may increase the well-being of the tourist in the city environment. Therefore, identified areas that will benefit from this collaboration among partners are smart tourism, public safety of tourism in the urban environment and eventually smart mobility.

Since many years, the use of VR in several museums in Lucca has been a focal point of interest of the city administration, leading to the application of VR to cultural heritage content such as the reconstruction of ancient monuments and city ancient areas. Thou, it is now more clear that the provision of smart video service and its applications, primarily targeted for tourists and visitors could enhance directly the way the city and its interesting points of cultural attractions as the Puccini museum are visited and explored by visitors and tourists.

In this context, the city of Lucca is aiming to collaborate with 5GCITY partners in designing and implementing Smart Museum services which can enhance the fruition of the most relevant museums of the city. Overall, visit to the different areas of the city can also be affected by the implementation of smart museum services.

It is also of particular interest for Lucca to extend to Public Safety Management the use of video applications that exploiting the capabilities of 5G can improve the safety of the urban environment for tourists and visitors, and may lead to an optimization of monitoring operations by the municipal police, otherwise performed manually. It is this the area of city surveillance, especially in relation to possible threats and crimes, which is already identified as one of the main areas of interest for the City of Lucca, as the mid/sized town is willing to increase the quality of the historic environment and safety for visitors, tourist and its citizen.

In this context, also future implementation of smart video services for the benefit of mobility (e.g. smart parking management) is an area were the city aims to enhance the collaboration.

For all these areas of interest, the municipality of Lucca has already involved all relevant stakeholders as museums and cultural institutions, agencies/offices for city security, the public surveillance operation centers, event organizers, local mobility agencies.

e) RAI

RAI Radiotelevisione Italiana, the Italian Public Service Broadcaster and Italy's largest radio--television broadcasting company, has played a major role in shaping the country's life and customs over the last decades. RAI started broadcasting its radio programmes in 1924 and nowadays broadcasts over 32.000 hours of television programmes (of which 75% are produced in-house) and 52.000 hours of radio programmes per year. Rai boasts national and international reach, high quality signal, coverage of the country's total area and reach of the Italian communities' world--wide. It is currently present on terrestrial and satellite digital platforms with 13 TV channels, most of them also available in High Definition. Moreover, its presence on the Web (<http://www.raisplay.it>) includes 14 live TV channels, 10 radio channels, web-TV thematic channels plus over one thousand on--demand programmes and more than 450 hours monthly published on--demand, targeting PCs, mobile devices (smartphones, tablets) and connected TVs.

For RAI, project results will be mainly constituted by the results of the experimental network pilots, in order to gain knowledge about new features offered by 5G technology in the areas of interest of a media company. RAI will exploit project results in two different areas, the final user area to enrich the television experience and in the television production area to use the new network to facilitate the covering of events, exploiting 5G features by providing new services: from audio/video UHD video distribution also as 360° video experience up to the virtual/augmented/mixed reality for immersive services. In particular:

- Knowledge in IP-end-to-end highly distributed broadcast production workflow, cloud/edge-based video and audio encoding, mixed reality for improved TV entertainment
- New TV formats enabled by new features offered by the 5GCity technologies
- Integration of the media company production workflow with new distributed edge network and computing technologies.

In particular RAI is collaborating with other partners of the project for the creation of state of the art television products in order to exploit 5GCity technologies in the area of the television production and in the area of distribution, taking into account UHD content and Immersive experiences in relevant cities. In this environment a particular focus of exploitation activities for RAI is about:

- OTT services in the 5G era.
- Cultural heritage for touristic and museums services.

In particular for the second point about Cultural Heritage RAI is collaborating with the other Italian partners of the project in the production of new content specifically studied for the city of Lucca also in collaboration with the "Giacomo Puccini Foundation" which lead the "Giacomo Puccini house Museum" (<http://www.puccinimuseum.org>).

In Lucca, as part of the project, RAI realized in collaboration with the Television Production Centre of Torino:

- A 4K-HDR A/V product to be used both for technical distribution tests on the 5G network and as a promotional/informative video of the project.
- A 360° product audio and video as an example of "immersive" experience focused mainly at the Casa Puccini Museum.

f) WindTre

Wind Tre is the leading operator in the Italian mobile market, with more than 30 million of customers and a market share above 37% for the mobile access. Wind Tre is achieving significant efficiencies and important investments in digital infrastructures. The move towards LTE and LTE-A has been carried out in all the geographic areas where such generations of cellular system were required according to service demand.

5GCity architecture is designed to be compliant to a wide range of use cases according to the fulfilled requirements, especially in terms of latency, resilience, coverage, and bandwidth. One of the challenges is to provide end-to-end network and cloud infrastructure slices over the same physical infrastructure to meet vertical-specific requirements as well as mobile broadband services in parallel. 5GCity has identified three

main scenarios which groups the project Use Cases, namely the Neutral Host, Industry vertical (Media and Entertainment) and city services.

In the first scenario (Neutral Host), 5GCity leverages its virtualization platform to enable the cities (or any infrastructure provider) to create dynamic end-to-end slices containing both virtualized edge and network resources and lease it to third-party operators or verticals. The scenario consists of managing the underlying physical infrastructure to offer a set of virtual resources to an operator, who builds, on top, its own services ready for end-user consumption.

The second scenario (Industry vertical) is strictly related to different aspects of the media and entertainment industry, which are strictly integrated into 5GCity project, and encompass all the Use Cases pivoting around video acquisition, editing and delivery.

The third scenario is related to Smart City which is tailored to the specific needs of a city (WindTre is focusing on the city of Lucca).

Concerning the second scenario, immersive experience with high quality video (HD or UHD videos) for tourists, including 3D video, 360-degree video, Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) applications, can be considered. The third scenario exploits the cities' surveillance cameras by deploying a virtualized monitoring service that can process video streams near cameras automatically to identify illegal dumping, and for autonomous mobility in the city to enhance public transportation.

Of course, the first scenario is a profitable enabler for all the use-cases belonging to the families of the first and second scenarios.

5G City is dealing with different financial relevant market sectors of the new technology era, namely the Virtualized Enhanced Packet Core (VEPC), the (Multi-access Mobile) Edge Computing and the Small Cells ones. Those enable flexible network slicing with the needed virtualized computing resources and a dense coverage to address the requirements of all the mentioned verticals. Wind Tre is exploring in 5G City how to evolve the business opportunities according to the current and expected requirements coming from its future customers, either business or consumer. As already discussed in the project, a business model could be based on an NH, as a Municipality, or an alternative option is that of joint/shared deployments of future networks, i.e., certain MNOs taking care of the deployment in agreed areas (or cities) in a "RAN-sharing" mode. As part of the agreement, other involved MNOs take care of the deployment in other areas. Nowadays, these joint deployments are a common practice in closed areas for DAS (Distributed Antenna Systems) deployments, and indeed there the biggest "obstacle" to the NH model, far beyond the other concerns. Although this cannot be a way of NH model, as the actor taking over the deployment is never "neutral", as is one of the MNOs that will provide services to end users, it is of high importance to study the pros and cons of these two models and identify some advantages of the NH over the joint model.

This work has already started and is going on in the project, and this is critical for an MNO as Wind Tre to fully understand the pros, cons and any possible implication of a given choice.

In general, it has been identified that NH is the best model overall. As said, NH offers network slices and the facilities to manage them. Network slices employ frequency resources. In principle, NH can have its own spectrum to share, or re-sell MNO's owned spectrum, but these are not always viable scenarios in some countries. The project with the multi-dimensional competences of its partners and looking at the worldwide context has analysed the issue and as concluded that an MNO cannot be the NH. But NH can provide network slices to an MNO as a client of its. The MNO can use its own frequency-chain to realize a full/end-to-end network slice and services (its client could be a vertical, as a content provider for live-streaming or VOD services).

Furthermore, Novel business models should target flexibility in resource allocation and scaling, billing but also in clients' requirements and type. Both B-to-B and B-to-C models are concerned. For example, value-added advs campaigns and services, as well as and OTTs as vertical in addition to the traditional TV broadcasters Should be supported by the new business models.

g) Incites

Incites is eager to participate in this joint exploitation activity by defining the appropriate business models, based on the ones described in this project, and supporting all the business coordination in any future commercial agreement.

h) CoDi

Immersive video proposed by Comunicare refers to the concept of the production to be treated. Since the verification of the virality and interest of the idea, to the conditions of concrete realization, with the involvement of actors / players / institutions / stakeholders or editors can converge in a sort of creative hub platform; that can reach also the realization of the content according to the conditions included in the final product, and the further visibility that the product itself could provide in other sectors.

As an example, a product created on Giacomo Puccini, his works or as RAI has already done in the Museum, can find a demonstrated interest not only in Lucca; but also globally, as a further promotion of the city, the music of the maestro, and as promotion for the territory.

The realization, for example, of a concert using immersive video at the Teatro del Giglio certainly has an important prominence on a global level, considering that the opera has a common language (Italian) and that this product can be reverberated in Barcelona at the Liceu or the Palau de la Musica, as well as in all the places dedicated to opera.

We cannot forget that Lucca has very interesting topics to explore, such as: photography (Photolux - World Press Photo), music (Summer Festival - Puccini - Boccherini), comics and gaming (Comics and Games), as Food & Wine (Chianti and prestigious production in the area). The city itself is also a magnificent “natural scenario” to represent.

It is our belief that the success of immersive video depends not only by the production, but in sharing, delivering the communication and involvement among interesting players in Europe.

i) Summary of the proposal

In the same way as in the Barcelona hub, this joint exploitation proposal is based on the Neutral Host capabilities and platform that is expected from the 5GCity project.

The scenario for the immersive video services in Smart Cities is very wide, and covers multiple sub-solutions that can be jointly exploited. Obviously, all of them need the basic capabilities of the inherent platform that in this case is supported by the Municipality of Lucca, both for the Facility Management role, and for the Smart City services user point of view.

Besides, the support of WindTre will allow (in case this Neutral Host model confirms his benefits through 5GCity over the stand-alone deployments) to count with at least one supporting mobile operator for the service. This support is mandatory in each country the solution is to be deployed, and needs to be addressed from the very beginning.

The participation of all the other partners has been justified in order to create this scenario, and to be properly exploited. Specific activities have been already proposed, providing small steps towards the final exploitation plan, such as the mentioned collaboration with Puccini Museum, or the clear interest of the Municipality of Lucca to re-use the immersive video services not only for tourism enhanced user experience, but also for security or smart parking services.

This service is also potentially exploitable in the other 5GCity locations, and in any other location where the platform (or similar Neutral Host platforms) can be deployed in the future.

4.2.3. Bristol Hub Joint Exploitation Plan

4.2.3.1. (360) Video content distribution in real time

One of the most promising scenarios for Bristol focus on how to produce and distribute (360) video contents in real time. The proposed solution, based on one of the use cases of the 5G City project, is expected to be jointly exploited by **RAI** and the **University of Bristol**, with the support from **Accelleran** for the integration within the infrastructure radio access and the business modelling of **Incites**, taking the proposed BM developed in the 5G City project as basis. In the following points it is described the expected participation and/or point of view from each partner.

a) RAI

RAI Radiotelevisione Italiana, the Italian Public Service Broadcaster and Italy's largest radio--television broadcasting company, has played a major role in shaping the country's life and customs over the last decades. RAI started broadcasting its radio programmes in 1924 and nowadays broadcasts over 32.000 hours of television programmes (of which 75% are produced in-house) and 52.000 hours of radio programmes per year. Rai boasts national and international reach, high quality signal, coverage of the country's total area and reach of the Italian communities' world--wide. It is currently present on terrestrial and satellite digital platforms with 13 TV channels, most of them also available in High Definition. Moreover, its presence on the Web (<http://www.raisplay.it>) includes 14 live TV channels, 10 radio channels, web-TV thematic channels plus over one thousand on--demand programmes and more than 450 hours monthly published on--demand, targeting PCs, mobile devices (smartphones, tablets) and connected TVs.

For RAI, project results will be mainly constituted by the results of the experimental network pilots, in order to gain knowledge about new features offered by 5G technology in the areas of interest of a media company. RAI will exploit project results in two different areas, the final user area to enrich the television experience and in the television production area to use the new network to facilitate the covering of events, exploiting 5G features by providing new services: from audio/video UHD video distribution also as 360° video experience up to the virtual/augmented/mixed reality for immersive services. In particular:

- Knowledge in IP-end-to-end highly distributed broadcast production workflow, cloud/edge-based video and audio encoding, mixed reality for improved TV entertainment
- New TV formats enabled by new features offered by the 5GCity technologies
- Integration of the media company production workflow with new distributed edge network and computing technologies.

In particular RAI is collaborating with other partners of the project for the creation of state of the art television products in order to exploit 5GCity technologies in the area of the television production and in the area of distribution, taking into account UHD content and Immersive experiences in relevant cities. In this environment a particular focus of exploitation activities for RAI is about:

- OTT services in the 5G era.
- Cultural heritage for touristic and museums services.

In particular for the first point, at this stage it is difficult to say if the Broadcaster or OTT services providers will need 5G. The end users will make the decision of adopting 5G based on the flexibility, additional functionality and the cost effectiveness that 5G will provide. We can expect that the video content distribution and services will evolve towards 5G and will use it as a complement to the already existing technologies e.g. the Television broadcasting ones.

For RAI the 5G technology is expected to build on and integrate the previous generations of wireless networks. 5G will support the expected broadcasters' mobile data growth, and at the same time will allow new services for final users and advertisement.

5G will bring network performance enhancements and agility in the network characteristics, and with that, will play an important role in supporting the growth and development of many industries, the broadcasting and media factories included.

b) University of Bristol

The University of Bristol as part of West of England Combined Authority to install 5G mobile technology and demonstrate use cases of immersive reality in historical locations will be interested to offer experimentation-as-services. A great opportunity for verticals interested in commercial services by using the 5GCity platform and infrastructure deployed as part of the 5G UK test network deployed in Roman Baths in Bath, Bristol's MShed museum and science centre We the Curious.

The 5GCity neutral host platform currently in deployment in the University of Bristol will facilitate multiple verticals interested in the development and test of pre-commercial or experimental contents and applications for immersive reality to slice the 5G infrastructure of 5G UK test network.

c) Accelleran

Accelleran plans to carry commercial exploitation of the following provided 5GCity components of the 5GCity platform infrastructure:

- Physical Small Cell product equipment (Hardware)
- Virtual dRAX RAN Control Plane intelligence product (Software)

With regards to the physical Small Cell product equipment, Accelleran would make commercial exploitation through the usual traditional revenue streams applied by infrastructure vendors, mainly:

- Physical Small Cell product equipment sales (CAPEX)
- Support and Maintenance contracts with neutral hosts (OPEX)

With regards to the virtual dRAX RAN Control Plane intelligence, the virtualisation and disaggregation of the RAN network components will bring new revenue streams paradigms (new in the RAN) similar to the software royalties of other software industries:

- Virtual dRAX RAN Control plane intelligence software product royalties (bundled with physical Small Cell product equipment sales or separate if the software runs managing compatible physical Small Cell products delivered by third party vendors)

Beyond these traditional and virtualised software revenues streams, Accelleran is willing to explore new paradigms (yet to be defined) whereby certain revenue streams could be linked to the added value services and use cases delivered over the infrastructure. This could be, as example, a percentage of the total revenue generated by these services/use cases provided to end users.

d) Incites

Incites is eager to participate in this joint exploitation activity by defining the appropriate business models, based on the ones described in this project, and supporting all the business coordination in any future commercial agreement.

e) Summary of the proposal

In the same way as in the Barcelona and Lucca hubs, this joint exploitation proposal is based on the Neutral Host capabilities and platform that is expected from the 5GCity project.

The scenario for the 360-video content distribution has been identified by traditional broadcasters as one of the key 5G scenarios to be covered. Due to the irruption of the new players in the content distribution market, basically OTT players, the real-time distribution of extremely-high quality video is an extremely interesting opportunity for traditional broadcasters, such as RAI.

The ability to use the Neutral Host infrastructure and platform created in 5GCity is of major interest in order to be able to offer these new services.

In this particular case, the potential cooperation among the interested players, such as RAI and the University of Bristol, can create the right proposition, supported by the specific customizations needed to this scenario done by one of the key owners of the technology behind it (i.e. Accelleran), and also combined with the business modelling provided by Incites.

As in the other scenarios, this proposal must be supported by the underlying platform and technology, and the players in charge of making it real, such as the Neutral Host provider or the mobile operator, so these functions will need to be also covered.

This service is also potentially exploitable in the other 5GCity locations, and in any other location where the platform (or similar Neutral Host platforms) can be deployed in the future.

5. Conclusions

This deliverable describes the results of dissemination, exploitation and standardization activities carried out during the Year 2 of the 5GCity project. In summary we can affirm that the consortium has successfully built a consistent and relevant impact through the first consolidated project results.

Regarding dissemination actions, we have to highlight during the Year 2 the relevant presence at international level events like SCEWC2018, SDN/NFV World Congress, and MWC2019, maximising the visibility of project concepts, progress, and results. The consortium has also achieved a high level of relevance participating in international conferences and publishing the project results. In this sense we have to highlight the good result in terms of published papers (9 out of 13 submissions), being most of these papers results of joint collaborations between 5GCity partners. For example, 5GCity has secured a good presence at the EuCNC 2019 with two papers in the main tracks, one paper in a special session, participation in two workshops and live outdoor and indoor demonstration of its UCs. The deliverable also identifies the main dissemination events for the next months.

In reference to standardization, 5GCity progressed as well on part of contribution to SDOs and open source community with direct code contribution to Unikraft XEN project, ETSI OSM, and Eclipse fog05.

The document also presents the revised individual exploitation plans and has identified joint exploitation plans per city hub as clusters of different partners: *“E2E Multi-carrier NH platform deployment and commercialization”* and *“Video acquisition service using dedicated slices of the NH infrastructure”* plans for the Barcelona hub, *“Immersive Video Services for Smart Cities”* for the Lucca hub, the plan and *“(360) Video content distribution in real time”* for the Bristol hub.

Overall, Year 2 has been very productive for the communications, dissemination, standardization, and exploitation activities in the project which shall continue in the next period until the end of the project. The project plans to participate in EuCNC 2019, organise two 5GCity Hackathons, host OSM Hackfest and participate in MWC2020 with demonstrations to promote the final results of the project.

5.1. Progress on 5GCity KPIs

Based on the KPIs identified in the 5GCity Description of Action, the progress achieved by the consortium during Year 2 is summarized in the following tables.

KPI Identifier	Description	Status
KPI-O1-1	White paper with the architecture	Planned for the final 6 months, once the Neutral Host deployment models will be consolidated for stakeholders/adopters
KPI-O1-2	Publication of the architecture published in at least two scientific/industrial journals	1 Journal publication achieved. Another publication under preparation
KPI-O1-3	At least one contribution to the 5G PPP architecture working group	5GCity representatives are discussing multiple whitepapers to be produced by 5G PPP working groups in 2019
KPI-O6-1	At least 20 publications in relevant conferences and journals	Y1. 8 accepted/published out of 9 submitted Y2. 11 accepted/submitted out of 13 submitted
KPI-O6-2	At least 2 contributions to standardization bodies.	Accepted contribution to ETSI OSM (VIM connector for Eclipse fog05)

		Project mentioned in the ETSI White Paper No. 20 “Developing Software for Multi-Access Edge Computing - 2nd edition”, in Annex B - Collaborative projects related to MEC. [ETSI-whitepaper].
KPI-O6-3	At least 2 white papers	Planned for the final 6 months
KPI-O6-4	At least 2 workshops organized.	2 workshops organized at EUCNC2018 + 1 special session on ITALIA5G at IOTTHINGS 2018 MILAN 1 Challenge and Workshop organized for Smart City Expo 2018 Barcelona 1 Special Session organized for EUCNC’ 19
KPI-O6-5	At least one pilot demo at MWC.	Neutral Host demo at MWC2019 / 5G Barcelona area

Table 5 – KPI progress as derived from 5GCity objectives

KPI	Description	KPI	Status
Open source contributions	Accepted contributions to open-source communities: (i) KVM community; (ii) QEMU developers’ community; (iii) XEN community; (iv) Open Data Plane (ODP) project; (v) OPNFV project; and (v) Contributions to ETSI OSM	At least 3 accepted contributions to different communities during project lifetime	Unikraft project continued as XEN project fog-05 started as Eclipse project Accepted contribution to ETSI OSM (VIM connector for Eclipse fog05)
Pilots and proof of concepts (PoCs)	Applications deployed in three cities: (i) Neutral host pilot (telecom pilot); (ii) Mobile backpack media unit (media pilot); (iii) UHD video distribution (media pilot); (iv) Video acquisition and edge/cloud production (media pilot); (v) Unauthorized waste dumping prevention (smart city pilot)	1 PoC pilot deployed per city; and one common pilot replicated in the three cities	Ongoing
Contribution to standards	Contributions to OpenFog consortium Contributions to ETSI NFV Other standards will be analysed in WP6 standardization task	At least 2 accepted contributions	ADLINK contributed to OpenFog Reference Architecture Project mentioned in the ETSI White Paper No. 20 “Developing Software for Multi-Access Edge Computing - 2nd edition”, in Annex B - Collaborative projects related to

			MEC. [ETSI-whitepaper].	
Industry events and ad-hoc meetings	<p>Organization of workshops in national / international events gathering cities, 5G, and edge technologies.</p> <p>Participation in the most relevant world-wide events: (i) Mobile World Congress; (ii) Smart Cities World Congress; (iii) Industrial IoT World Congress; (iv) Fog computing Expo; (v) ITS World Congress; and (vi) TV Markets, European Digital Forum, UltraHD 4K Summit</p>	At least 2 workshops organized, at least participation in 2 industry events per year	3 events executed (16 th EU Digital Forum Lucca, 5G Barcelona events around MWC19)	
Publications	Industry-related	Publications of White papers, magazines, technology roadmaps, and industry-led journals	At least 5	3 newsletters issued Others planned for next year
	Scientific	Publication of scientific results to high-impact journals and leading conferences	At least 15	19 accepted/published out of 22 submitted (Y1+Y2)
	EU events	Presentation of 5GCity results, research and innovation activities, booth and demo set up	At least 1 participation in EU events per year	Yearly participation to EUCNC Participation with demos at ICT2018 Wien
Web site, social networks, press releases	Web portal and social media mechanisms will be employed to demonstrate the potential benefits of the solution that will be developed to highlight 5GCity use cases	Public website; 2 newsletters per year;	Website online 2 newsletters published for Y1	
Web site, social networks, press releases	Web portal and social media mechanisms will be employed to demonstrate the potential benefits of the solution that will be developed to highlight 5GCity use cases	1 social networking tool utilized	Twitter+LinkedIn+Y outube accounts activated and highly visible	

Table 6 - 5GCity objectives dissemination specific objectives

6. Abbreviations and Definitions

6.1. Abbreviations

5G IA	5G Infrastructure Association
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
MANO	Management and Orchestration
NFV	Networks Function Virtualization
NFVI	Networks Function Virtualization Infrastructure
NS	Network Services
PPP	Public Private partnership
SDO	Standard Developing Organization
VNF	Virtual Network Function
WG	Working group
WP	Work Package

6.2. Definitions

No definition is introduced by this document

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